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Ecosystem Services Provided by Permaculture

Doctoral thesis

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Annotation

This thesis explores the sustainability potential of permaculture, a socio-ecological movement that seeks to ecologise agriculture and generate benefits across ecological, economic, and social dimensions. The research applies an integrated methodological framework grounded in the concepts of ecosystem services and nature's contributions to people. Using a multidisciplinary mixed-methods design, the study assesses material, regulating, and non-material contributions across eight permaculture farms—six located in Czechia and two in Belgium.

Regulating services were evaluated through quantitative biophysical field measurements, material services through a combination of ecological and social science approaches, and non-material services through qualitative inquiry. This holistic design allowed for the integration of ecological data with social science perspectives, offering a comprehensive assessment of permaculture's contributions to multifunctionality, resilience, and sustainability.

Results show that permaculture spans all domains of ecosystem benefits, but its particular strength lies in mobilising relational values that encourage biodiversity-supporting practices, which in turn underpin regulating services. Permaculture demonstrates high capacity to provide regulating services and can contribute valuable insights for sustainable food futures. A slightly lower delivery of material services may inform a debate about land sharing versus land sparing in agriculture and about diet change in exchange for nutrients diversity, leading to sustainable solutions based on broad values of respect, health and prosperity.

Anotace

Tato práce zkoumá potenciál permakultury pro udržitelnost. Permakultura je socio-ekologické hnutí usilující o ekologizaci zemědělství tak, aby přinášelo ekologické, ekonomické ale i sociální benefity. Metodologický rámec výzkumu zahrnuje koncepty ekosystémových služeb a přínosů přírody lidem. Pomocí multidisciplinárního kombinovaného výzkumu byly hodnoceny materiální, regulační a nemateriální přínosy na osmi permakulturních farmách – šesti v České republice a dvou v Belgii.

Regulační služby byly vyhodnocovány na základě kvantitativních biofyzikálních měření v terénu, materiální služby kombinací ekologických a sociologických metod a nemateriální služby pomocí kvalitativních sociologických přístupů. Toto holistické pojetí umožnilo propojení ekologických dat s poznatky společenských věd a poskytlo komplexní hodnocení příspěvků permakultury k multifunkčnosti, odolnosti a udržitelnosti zemědělství.

Výsledky ukazují, že permakultura zahrnuje všechny oblasti ekosystémových přínosů, avšak její silnou stránkou je mobilizace relačních hodnot, které v lidech mobilizují managementové praktiky, které přispívají k biodiverzitě. Biodiverzita je základnou regulačních služeb. Permakultura vykazuje vysokou schopnost poskytovat regulační služby a může nabídnout cenné podněty pro udržitelné potravinové systémy budoucnosti. Poněkud nižší úroveň materiálních služeb může přispět do debaty o sdílení versus vyčleňování půdy v zemědělství, jakož i o roli změny jídelníčku směrem k nutriční rozmanitosti. Obě tyto debaty jsou relevantní pro udržitelná řešení založená na širokých hodnotách jako jsou respekt, zdraví a prosperita.

Key words

Permaculture, agroecology, ecosystem services, Nature's Contribution to People, relational values, sustainable food futures, biodiversity

Klíčová slova

Permakultura, agroekologie, ekosystémové služby, příspěvky přírody lidem, relační hodnoty, udržitelná potravinová budoucnost, biodiverzita

Declaration

I declare that I have prepared the submitted thesis independently and have used only the sources and literature listed. I hereby give permission for this thesis to be made available in the relevant library of Charles University and through the electronic database of university qualification theses in the Charles University repository and to be used for study purposes in accordance with copyright law. I also declare that the thesis has not been used to obtain another or the same degree.

Prague, 3 October 2025

Linda Blättler

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List of abbreviations

EUCRA	European Climate Risk Assessment
MA	Millenium Ecosystem Assessment
NCP	Nature's Contribution to People
PDC	Permaculture Design Certificate Course
RV	Relational value

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1 Introduction

1.1. Ecosystem services in agriculture

1.1.2. Ecosystem services and Nature's contributions to people

Ecosystems provide humanity with many services that not just contribute to our well-being but are essential for physical human existence. Early mentions of 'nature's services' appeared in the late 20th century (Daily et al., 1997; Ehrlich & Mooney, 1983), culminating in the *Millennium Ecosystem Assessment* (MA, 2005), which defined ecosystem services (ES) as '**benefits people obtain from ecosystems**' and formalized four groups of ES: provisioning, regulating, supporting¹, and cultural services. Although holistic in scope, the MA framework has been criticised for focusing primarily on instrumental values, while underrepresenting intrinsic and relational values that also underpin human–nature interactions (Chan, Guerry, et al., 2012; Díaz et al., 2015, 2018a; Pascual et al., 2017). This led to the development of the concept of *Nature's Contributions to People* (NCP), which broadened the ES framework. NCP are '**all the contributions, both positive and negative, of living nature (diversity of organisms, ecosystems, and their associated ecological and evolutionary processes) to people's quality of life**' (Díaz et al., 2018a). It distinguishes 18 categories within three main groups—material, regulating, and non-material cultural within the '*generalizing perspective*', which is more typical of the natural sciences and economics. It also acknowledges the '*context-specific categories*', a perspective more common in local or Indigenous knowledge systems. Despite conceptual differences (Kadykalo et al. 2019), the ES and NCP frameworks can be used synergistically and are increasingly treated as complementary (Zoeller and Cumming 2024; Moreira et al. 2025). Figure 1 from Díaz et al. (2018b) illustrates this development, showing the transmission and overlap of ES groups between the MA and NCP frameworks.

¹ In MA (2005), supporting services were defined as underlying ecological processes that enable the other three groups of ES. Because overlaps and double counting was discovered with many regulating ES, in the later works this category was dropped (Haines-Young & Potschin, 2018). These processes are now usually called 'ecosystem functions'.

Figure 1. Evolution of nature's contributions to people (NCP) and other major categories in the Intergovernmental Platform for Biodiversity and Ecosystem services (IPBES) with respect to the concepts of ES and human well-being as defined in MA. Source: (Díaz et al., 2018b).

While the MA and NCP frameworks are widely used in scientific research to capture the full range of human–nature relationships (Díaz et al., 2018b; Kadykalo et al., 2019), other classifications serve different purposes—for example *The Economics of Ecosystems and Biodiversity* (TEEB, 2008) focuses on the economic valuation of ecosystem services to inform policy, whereas *Common International Classification of Ecosystem*

Services (CICES) offers a standardized typology for ecosystem accounting and indicator development (Haines-Young & Potschin, 2018).

Recent systematic reviews highlight the NCP approach's unique strength in emphasizing relational values and mutual interactions between humans and nature, while also identifying limitations in addressing comprehensive ecosystem components (Moreira et al., 2025). This underscores the necessity of using complementary frameworks to ensure a holistic understanding of ecosystem dynamics.

In this thesis, MA and NCP concepts are both used complementary. The reason is (1) that they are both well established in the literature and (2) for an analysis of agricultural systems they offer a broad basis of services. I use the NCP groups material, non-material and regulating. The term 'service' or 'ES' is equal to 'contribution' or 'benefit' in the coming text. I refer to:

- **material ES** as to substances, objects, or other material elements from nature that directly sustain people's physical existence and material assets. They are typically physically consumed in the process of being experienced—for example, when organisms are transformed into food, energy, or materials for ornamental purposes (Díaz et al., 2018a),
- **regulating ES** as functional or structural aspects of organisms and ecosystem that modify environmental conditions experienced by people and/or regulate the generation of material and non-material contributions. They often affect quality of life in indirect ways (Díaz et al., 2018a).
- **non-material ES** (benefits) as intangible aspects of well-being (Chan et al., 2016; Chan, Satterfield, et al., 2012; Gould et al., 2015) that are co-produced through human–ecosystem interactions (Fish et al., 2016; Hirons et al., 2016).

1.1.3. Agriculture as a complex socio-ecological system

Early agroecological research presented farming systems as parts of larger ecological systems, interacting with natural processes like nutrient cycling, pollination, and energy flows (Altieri, 1999). That means that ecosystem processes impaired for example by climate change, lead to declined crop production, which in turn threatens feeding humanity and its sustainable development (EUCRA, 2024; United Nations, 2019).

Ecosystem processes can also be impaired by management practices that do not support biodiversity upon which they depend (Altieri, 1999). In general, according to IPBES, ‘unsustainable agriculture’ refers to cropland and grazing systems that degrade land by overusing chemical inputs, expanding into natural ecosystems. It is also driven by harmful economic incentives and weak governance—leading to biodiversity loss, reduced ES, and broader environmental degradation (IPBES, 2018, 2019, 2025). This is a result of the last two hundred years, when food production systems were managed as if they were engineered: mechanization increased and diverse ecosystem functions to support biomass creation were supplemented and replaced by human inputs (Chapman et al., 2017). For this way of farming different names with a slightly different meaning are used, such as ‘modern’, ‘conventional’ or ‘industrial’ agriculture. Since none of them has been clearly defined in scientific framing and they all have historical connotations, we should rather concentrate on what can make agriculture sustainable (Sumberg & Giller, 2022).

To ‘return’ the systems perspective to agriculture, early ES literature highlighted the agriculture’s reliance on regulating services such as pollination, soil fertility, pest control and water regulation (Swift et al., 2004; Zhang et al., 2007). Swinton et al. (2007) and Power (2010) expanded this view by emphasising that agriculture not only depends on ecosystem services, but also provides them. While it is a major supplier of provisioning services such as food, fibre, and fuel, agriculture also has the potential—if managed sustainably—to contribute to regulating services like carbon sequestration, water regulation, and biodiversity habitat (Vanbergen et al., 2020). At the same time, it is critically dependent on regulating and supporting services such as nutrient cycling, soil formation, and climate regulation, many of which are degraded by intensive farming practices. Similarly, in their conceptual work, Haines-Young and Potschin (2012) postulated that biodiversity underpins the ecological structures and processes that generate ecosystem services. Agriculture is both a driver of biodiversity change (through intensification, land-use change, pollution, etc.) and a system dependent on biodiversity for its functioning. This was reflected in later studies about biodiversity decline and unsustainable agriculture’s leading role in it (Dainese et al., 2019; Foley et al., 2011; Garbach et al., 2014; IPBES, 2019; MA, 2005; Power, 2010; Richardson et al., 1996; Tilman et al., 2001; Tscharrntke et al., 2005)

Because management decisions strongly influence the capacity of agroecosystems to provide a full range of ES (Bengochea Paz et al., 2020; DeClerck et al., 2016; Foley et al., 2005; Power, 2010; Zhang et al., 2007), the historical prioritisation of provisioning services often came at the expense of regulating and cultural services. According to IPBES (2019), 14 out of 18 NCP categories are degraded, but the agricultural production tripled since 1970. It became clear that agricultural unsustainable intensification often causes soil degradation, disrupts nutrient and water cycles, increases pollution, and accelerates biodiversity loss (Emmerson et al., 2016; Ruiz-Martinez et al., 2015) and threatens the sustainability of agricultural ecosystems (IPBES, 2019).

Therefore, empirical studies have examined ecosystem services in agricultural contexts from various perspectives. Felipe-Lucia *et al.* (2020) and Garbach *et al.* (2017) analysed trade-offs and synergies between provisioning, regulating, and cultural services in multifunctional landscapes. They found that trade-offs often occur between provisioning services (crop yield) and regulating or cultural services (like pollination, biodiversity, or recreation) and that synergies were more likely among regulating services (e.g., water quality and pollination often improved together). Low-intensity landscapes showed more synergies, high-intensity more trade-offs. Garbach *et al.* (2017) further noted that certain “win–win” practices—such as adding flower strips, reducing pesticide use, and maintaining hedgerows—can increase synergies between biodiversity and regulating services without strongly reducing yields, although these require careful, locally adapted design. These practices can inspire conventional agriculture, demonstrating that small changes in management can secure both food production and ES functions.

Several authors demonstrated how diversified farming systems can enhance pollination, pest control, and soil health while reducing reliance on external inputs (Hass et al., 2018; Holt et al., 2016; Kremen & Miles, 2012). Stavi *et al.* (2016) and Williams & Hedlund and (2014) emphasised the role of soil-related services in sustaining agricultural productivity, while Robertson *et al.* (2014) and Chapman *et al.* (2017) showed that even intensive row-crop systems can be managed to provide services such as pest control, clean water, climate regulation through greenhouse gas mitigation, and soil fertility alongside high yields. These examples illustrate that even conventional, high-yield systems can be

“renovated” to support multiple ES through practices like diversifying crop rotations, integrating perennials, and maintaining non-crop habitat patches.

Apart from efforts to incorporate these practices into current agriculture and make it more sustainable—securing natural resources and ES while enhancing agriculture’s role in meeting food and nutrition security demands (Foley et al., 2011)—there is also a call for systemic, integrated strategies (European Commission, 2024) that enable adaptation at the whole-systems level (EUCRA, 2024) and support the paradigm-shift (IPES-Food, 2018). Poorly informed land-use decisions could risk socio-ecological collapse (Bengochea Paz et al., 2020), which makes this call urgent.

1.1.4. Transition to sustainable agriculture

Given the well-documented degradation of regulating and cultural services under unsustainable agriculture and intensification, alternative farming methods and systems have emerged to restore ecosystem functions while maintaining food production. Since the term ‘alternative’ could automatically evoke notions of ‘good’ (Sumberg & Giller, 2022), it may be more appropriate to frame these as ‘sustainable’, which leaves greater space for inclusive thinking. Here, the adjective ‘alternative’ is used specifically to denote a departure from the unsustainable agrifood paradigm, as in Zhang (2024).

These alternative farming approaches—including agroecology, agroforestry, holistic grazing management, organic farming, land-sharing agriculture, conservation agriculture, restorative agriculture, regenerative agriculture, and permaculture—have emerged as potential solutions to sustainable agricultural challenges. Many of them are based on traditional low-intensity agricultural management practices (Altieri, 1999; IPBES, 2019) that have fostered the development and maintenance of unique floral and faunal communities and habitat conditions, thereby supporting biodiversity and the supply of multiple important ES (Bank et al., 2025).

The goal of these alternative socio-ecological food systems is to shift from a focus solely on material returns to a more holistic approach to food sourcing. Food production practices can harm ecosystems, but they can also enhance them by improving the quality of underlying ecological processes, thereby supporting long-term service provision. Various authors argue that agriculture should not be exempt from nature conservation (Fischer

et al., 2008; Kremen & Miles, 2012; McNeely & Scherr, 2003; TEEB, 2015). The debate on agricultural land-sharing emphasizes integrating conservation spaces through practices like agroforestry and diversified land use to secure biodiversity and promote sustainable food production (DeClerck et al., 2011; Remans et al., 2015; Wood et al., 2015a).

The concept of ES has become central in evaluating different alternative agricultural systems and methods (Bengtsson et al., 2005; Boeraeve et al., 2020a; Bucheli & Bokelmann, 2017; Garbach et al., 2017; Jose, 2009; Kay et al., 2018; Kuyah et al., 2018; Mäder et al., 2002; Ramachandran Nair et al., 2010; Reiff et al., 2024; Rey Benayas & Bullock, 2012; Stavi et al., 2016; Torralba et al., 2016), especially because it enables a “win-win” scenario (Power, 2010) and favours integrated land, water and living resources management to promote conservation and sustainable use equitably (DeClerck et al., 2016). It emphasizes the contribution of regulating ES and ecosystem functions (formerly ‘supporting ES’) to the principal system outcome (yields for food provision) and therefore the fact that sustainable food production is an emergent property of multiple interacting ES rather than a single service itself (DeClerck et al., 2016).

When naturally occurring regulating ES are depleted, they are usually replaced by external inputs. This replacement often generates negative externalities—sometimes described as “disservices”—from agriculture (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005). For agriculture to fully realise its potential in contributing to multiple sustainability targets, it must bring together agricultural and conservation sciences through the lens of ES (DeClerck et al., 2016).

There is already compelling evidence from agronomic and ecological research that an agricultural system that incorporates perennality, species diversity and landscape heterogeneity enhance provisioning and regulating ES at the same time (Hirschfeld & Van Acker, 2020; Kreitzman et al., 2022; Redlich et al., 2018; Scott et al., 2022; Weißhuhn et al., 2017). This logic builds on a widely discussed hypothesis that agroecosystems should mimic natural ecosystems in their structure and composition, since structure and composition are key factors in ES provision (Malézieux, 2012).

The ES framework can therefore be well used when evaluating possible future agricultural systems, since they will be required to provide multifunctionality and resilience anyway (Boeraeve et al., 2020a; DeClerck et al., 2016). Framing agriculture in this way

emphasises that sustainable food production is not the outcome of a single ES, but of a dynamic interplay among many. This perspective also highlights the need for farming approaches that can deliberately integrate ecological processes into production systems, moving beyond mitigation of harms towards actively enhancing ecosystem functions that are necessary for delivering ES.

1.1.5. Assessment of ecosystem services in agroecosystems

The assessment of ES is a systematic process to evaluate the benefits ecosystems provide to people, using approaches tailored to the nature of each service group (Bank et al., 2025).

- **Material services** are most commonly quantified in physical units—such as crop yields, timber volumes, livestock numbers or water provision—which may then be translated into monetary values when marketed. However, many material benefits, such as subsistence production, wild foods, medicinal plants, or fuelwood, are not fully captured in markets, so non-market valuation methods are often needed to complement physical accounting (Boeraeve et al., 2020; Swinton et al., 2007).
- **Regulating services** are usually assessed through biophysical methods that measure ecological condition variables relevant to agroecosystems, such as soil nutrient status, or plant community composition. These assessments often rely on ecological field experiments and data collection, long-term monitoring, or synthesis through literature meta-analyses (Bank et al., 2025).
- **Non-material services** require different approaches, since they are relational and perception-based. They draw on environmental sciences, sociology, psychology and economics. Socio-cultural non-monetary valuation methods—including interviews, questionnaires, participatory workshops, observation methods or document analysis—are commonly used to capture qualitative contributions such as recreation, identity, knowledge and learning. Socio-economic monetary methods (e.g. travel cost, hedonic pricing) are also applied to capture the quantitative value of these services (Cheng et al., 2019) but it is challenging (Swinton et al., 2007).

Integrated approaches aim to combine ecological data with social perceptions to better reflect the full societal importance of ecosystems and their benefits for sustainability and human well-being (Boeraeve et al., 2015; de Groot et al., 2010). Recent reviews emphasise methodological pluralism and the need to apply such assessments across multiple scales, from farm plots to entire landscapes (Bank et al., 2025; Boeraeve et al., 2020)

1.2. Permaculture

In chapter 1. 1. 4., sustainable alternatives to status quo agriculture were presented in the light of current research on ES. According to Zhang (2024), only two of the approaches discussed—permaculture and agroecology—together with ‘alternative food networks’, aim at reconfiguring the broader food system and extend beyond individual farms to envision systemic transformation. In this thesis, I focus more deeply on permaculture.

1.2.2. What is permaculture

Permaculture is a social agroecological grassroots movement based on ethical principles that emerged over 40 years ago as a proactive response to industrial agriculture. It critiques the large-scale cultivation of monocultures reliant on heavy machinery and large quantities of chemicals that degrade the soil and contribute to various environmental issues, including greenhouse gas emissions (Krebs & Bach, 2018; Mollison & Holmgren, 1978). Today, permaculture is best understood as both a design framework and a grassroots movement that seeks to create resilient, multifunctional socio-ecological systems.

The concept of ‘*permanent culture*’ originated in Australia with Bill Mollison. While working as a wildlife scientist, he was struck by the abundance and interconnectedness of rainforest ecosystems. Concerned about soil degradation caused by industrial farming methods in Tasmania, he sought to develop stable agricultural systems as an alternative. Permaculture emerged as pioneering work in perennial agriculture, grounded in observations of ecological succession in natural ecosystems (Mollison & Holmgren, 1978). Its

origins were also strongly influenced by Meadows *et al.*'s *The Limits to Growth* (Mollison & Holmgren, 1978, preface to 2019 edition).²

Permaculture, now a popular movement with a global profile and thousands of practitioners (Ferguson & Lovell, 2014; Fiebrig *et al.*, 2020) has never entered the mainstream. As co-founder David Holmgren reflected in 2019, in the foreword to the facsimile edition of *Permaculture One*, it was 'muddied by the swirling waters of popular culture that propelled it beyond its academic and countercultural origins'. He added, however, that permaculture remains highly relevant: because its solutions have always been biological and community-oriented, they are well suited to today's sustainability challenges.

The definition of permaculture has evolved significantly:

- 1978: an "integrated, evolving system of perennial or self-perpetuating plant and animal species useful to man... a complete agricultural ecosystem, modelled on existing but simpler examples" (Mollison & Holmgren, 1978)
- 1988: broadened to "the conscious design and maintenance of agriculturally productive ecosystems which have the diversity, stability, and resilience of natural ecosystems... the harmonious integration of landscape and people" (Mollison, 1988)
- 2002: reframed by Holmgren as "the use of systems thinking and design principles that provide the organising framework for implementing the vision" expressed earlier (Holmgren, 2002).

Historically, in the early 1900s the term "*permanent agriculture*" was used in English in the same sense as "*sustainable*". Later it became associated with farming systems incorporating perennial species, particularly trees (Ferguson & Lovell, 2014). Perenniality was seen as a way to reduce compaction, erosion and disruption of soil biota (Mollison, 1988). Permaculture thus originally focussed on the management of land and nature stewardship involving its design and ethical principles, but later the same principles were also

² Interestingly, the authors of permaculture stated in 1978 that the damage done to productive lands by agriculture will only be apparent when the "high-energy society reaches its energy limits". Apparently, the issues related to agricultural land have become urgent even before the human society reaches this milestone.

applied to other domains of human life, so that the meaning of permaculture morphed rather into *'permanent culture'* (Holmgren, 2002).

In recent scholarship, permaculture is variously described as:

- *a theory for diversified farming systems guided by 12 principles within a holistic sustainability concept* (Fiebrig et al., 2020),
- *a systems approach to farm design that mimics natural processes and operates within ecological boundaries* (UNCCD, 2022),
- *an alternative agroecological movement emphasising its social dimensions* (Ferguson & Lovell, 2014),
- *a popular educational movement in socio-ecological contexts* (Henfrey, 2018).

These definitions highlight four components within permaculture—each of them may mean ‘permaculture’ as such: the international movement, the worldview disseminated by it, the design system, and the set of associated practices (Ferguson & Lovell, 2014). While Zhang (2024) positions permaculture as a ‘sustainable agriculture system’ *on the same level as agroecology*, others tend to understand permaculture *as part of agroecology*, also because its techniques are rarely unique to permaculture—they are often shared with agroecology, agroforestry and indigenous land use (Morel et al., 2024).

What makes permaculture unique, is its emphasis on the **design of the whole system** and its **ethical foundations** (Shrestha & Horwitz, 2024). Emphasis on perennials, polycultures and zone design might be regarded as compulsory characteristics for applied permaculture on the other hand (Hirschfeld & Van Acker, 2020).

1.2.3. Operationalization of permaculture in this study

In my thesis, I examine permaculture mainly in its original definition from 1988 (Mollison, 1988), as

“The conscious design and maintenance of agriculturally productive ecosystems which have the diversity, stability, and resilience of natural ecosystems. It is the harmonious integration of landscape and people, providing their food, energy, shelter, and other material and non-material needs in a sustainable way”.

This definition clearly states the core ideas that are linked to ES in permaculture systems:

- It is a nature-based system (generating regulating services)
- It provides people with material services and goods
- It provides people with non-material contributions
- It is sustainable

These core ideas will later find expression in Chapter 1. 3. Research questions.

1.2.4. Permaculture design

From its inception, permaculture was strongly influenced by systems ecology, particularly the work of Howard Odum, who viewed productive landscapes as ecological systems in which relationships, interactions, and energy flows are more significant than individual elements (Mollison & Holmgren, 1978, Ferguson & Lovell, 2014).

Therefore, there has always been an emphasis on designing the food growing space, however big or small, as one system within other systems. As articulated in the 1988 definition, these productive ecosystems should have “the resilience, diversity and stability of natural ecosystems”. Developing resilience to disturbances is a major theme in permaculture design. Elements are designed to be as autonomous as possible, ensuring continuity of critical system functions under stress (Holmgren, 2002). For example, resilience is expressed in crop selection: not necessarily choosing the highest-yielding varieties, but those that balance productivity with stability (Holmgren, 2002). In this sense, resilience—understood as flexibility rather than rigidity—is at the core of permaculture thinking. It produces dynamic stability; a quality Holmgren applies on the whole society in the times of unpredictable changes.

1.2.5. Permaculture ethics and principles

Informed by ecology, sustainability, environmental philosophy and traditional ecological knowledge (Le Vasseur in (Swinton et al., 2007; Thompson & Kaplan, 2014) three ethics of permaculture design were introduced by Holmgren (2002)— “*Earth care, People care, Fair share*”. The first one recognizes the Earth as the source of life and entails not

just protecting it from human damage, but actively regenerate ecological systems. 'People care' concerns care for ourselves and others, emphasising community self-reliance, health and well-being. 'Fair share', originally called 'return of surplus', is about setting limits to consumption and redistributing surpluses of any kind—time, money, harvest, knowledge) to support the two previous principles. Holmgren (2002) interprets this as voluntary simplicity and modesty.

This ethical background has been part of the permaculture idea since the beginning. As the authors state, for a survival of a society, there have to be values, directions, and ethics—these are the conditions for a society to control its future destiny (Mollison & Holmgren, 1978). Holmgren (2002) adds that the problems of our current 'multifold crises' are ethical at core.

For practitioners to be able to give these three ethical principles a real form when designing permaculture ecosystems, 12 permaculture design principles, rooted in systems ecology, were developed: Observe and interact, Catch and store energy, Obtain a yield, Apply self-regulation and accept feedback, Use and value renewable resources and services, Produce no waste, Design from patterns to details, Integrate rather than segregate, Use small and slow solutions, Use and value diversity, Use edges and value the marginal, and Creatively use and respond to change (Figure 2). Holmgren (2002) points out that their understanding has to stay dynamic, since 'any set of principles that has been found useful needs to be constantly questioned and further articulated to help us to recognise the creative solutions more clearly'.

Figure 2. Ethical principles (middle) surrounded by 12 design principles with a short explanation.

1.2.6. Permaculture in science

Ferguson & Lovell's (2014) early review already noted that permaculture knowledge, despite the wide practical spread, was largely confined to grey literature and practitioner networks, with little presence in peer-reviewed journals. Out of 230 publications in English, 32 of them were peer-reviewed journal articles. This highlighted a disconnect from mainstream science. More recently, Taylor (2025) provides the most comprehensive bibliometric overview to date, analysing 975 publications across four languages. He identified 364 journal peer-reviewed articles. His findings confirm that while permaculture has begun to appear more frequently in technical journals—especially in recent years—it remains only partly integrated into mainstream scientific discourse.

According to my own scope review, a number of studies in various disciplines have explored permaculture's potential as a transformative (Hathaway, 2015; Zhang, 2024),

sustainable (Morel et al., 2024; Padmavathy & Poyyamoli, 2011; Shrestha & Horwitz, 2024; Veteto & Lockyer, 2013; Vitari & David, 2017) or regenerative (Ferguson & Lovell, 2014; Habib & Fadaee, 2022; McLennon et al., 2021; McManus, 2010; Rhodes, 2015) agrifood system, most research remains theoretical in nature. Some studies explored permaculture's ethical dimensions (Centemeri, 2019; de la Bellacasa, 2010) positioning it not only as an agricultural technique but also as a movement with political and ethical transformational potential.

The majority of studies that looked at real examples of permaculture projects or ideas were of social sciences and focussed on the movement or a particular permaculture community itself and studied its identity, narratives, dynamics or interaction with other systems (Ferguson & Lovell, 2015; Ingram, 2018; Ingram et al., 2014; Kolářová, 2023; Martín et al., 2023; Suh, 2014). A number of other studies have suggested that permaculture should be included in the curriculum of a particular field of study because of its promising prospects (Henfrey, 2018; Lebo & Eames, 2015; Liu et al., 2018; Roux-Rosier et al., 2018; Veteto & Lockyer, 2013; Vitari & David, 2017).

Very few empirical studies on a farm level were done that studied their social, economic or ecological impact. Ferguson & Lovell (2017, 2019) studied how involvement with permaculture contributes to labour productivity on a sample of over 30 farms in the US or to the diversification of livelihoods in the same places. There is also a study evaluating the financial viability of a small-scale permaculture farm in France (Morel *et al.*, 2016).

Although theoretical in nature, the review of Krebs & Bach (2018), opened the floor for discussing the practical impact of permaculture in relation to ES. The authors claim that the holistic nature of the permaculture approach makes it a candidate for provisioning a wide array of ES. They analysed each of the 12 design principles and its alignment with established ecological and agroecological knowledge.

Studies about ecological impact of permaculture practices usually examine selected specific aspects of permaculture practice. A recent one addresses perenniality, diversity and landscape heterogeneity (Hirschfeld & Van Acker, 2020). Another study deals with soil changes after several years of applying permaculture practices on a farm in France (de Tombeur et al., 2018). Small water retention bodies were also explored on a permaculture farm in Spain regarding their efficiency (Fiebrig & Van Wiel, 2020).

Two recent empirical studies add slowly to the discussion that also my thesis wants to address. One investigated permaculture farms in Germany, with focus on soil quality and biodiversity (Reiff et al., 2024). Similarly, Williamson *et al.* (2024) examined permaculture plots in England, concentrating on soil fertility and microbial communities. The aforementioned authors also published a study about the crop productivity of permaculture this year (Reiff et al., 2025).

1.2.7. Research gaps

The previously mentioned scientific studies about permaculture show clearly that there is lack of *empirical testing of the impacts of permaculture principles and practices on agroecosystems, their resilience, ecological quality and their regenerative potential* (Fiebrig et al., 2020, 2020; Krebs & Bach, 2018; Ferguson, 2014). In 2014, Ferguson & Lovell (2014) specified that as agroecosystems are expected to provide multiple ES in the future, the role of configuration/design in supporting these services could be crucial. A similar gap is identified by Krebs & Bach (2018). Unresearched topics mentioned by both are for example: design, perenniality, diversity, patterns, functional relationships. Criteria for the evaluation could then be of two types: ecosystem mimicry and system optimization (Ferguson & Lovell, 2014; Krebs & Bach, 2018).

Fiebrig *et al.* (2020) directly calls for reliable data on ES gain through permaculture to help the concept to be valued by society and eligible for compensation.

Assessments of agricultural socio-ecological systems through the lens of ES was recommended many times to bring resilience to them (Boeraeve et al., 2020; DeClerck et al., 2016; MA, 2005; Power, 2010; Robertson et al., 2014; Swinton et al., 2007).

The key research gap in permaculture overlaps with that in ES and NCP assessments: what is the direct impact of human activities on nature and ecosystems and their feedback on the co-production of ES or NCP to achieve sustainability goals (Mastrángelo et al., 2019).

1.3. Research questions

This thesis addresses questions about permaculture's ability to create nature-like, resilient ecosystems while simultaneously producing food. This focus aligns with research gaps identified in the literature.

Moreover, the thesis examines whether permaculture has the potential to contribute to a sustainable transformation of agriculture. To assess this, its multifunctionality must be tested, which can be effectively evaluated through the framework of ecosystem services (ES).

On this basis, the study seeks to answer the following research questions (RQ):

- **RQ1:** What kinds of ecosystem services do permaculture ecosystems provide, and how do they span material, regulating, and non-material domains?
- **Sub-question:** Are the ecosystem services provided by permaculture ecosystems more similar to those of natural ecosystems or to conventional agricultural ecosystems?
- **RQ2:** To what extent can the ecosystem services provided by permaculture contribute to multifunctionality and resilience in future food systems?

2 Methodology

2.1. Broad methodological framework

Given the holistic nature of both permaculture and the ES framework, this socio-ecological study adopts an integrated methodological approach that combines positivist and constructivist epistemologies to examine the tangible and non-material benefits of permaculture ecosystems. Such interdisciplinarity is crucial for strengthening the long-term sustainability of ecosystem services and for ensuring their equitable access and provision (DeClerck et al., 2016).

For RQ1, I employed a combination of methods from the biophysical sciences and the social sciences. Because material, regulating, and non-material services are inherently different in their nature, they require different assessment strategies (Bank et al., 2025), as is shown in Figure 3.

- (i) mixed ecological and social science methods for material services and biodiversity
- (ii) quantitative biophysical field measurements for regulating services
- (iii) qualitative social science methods for non-material services

Figure 3. Methodological approaches applied to address RQ1.

These methods will be applied as part of the field research to collect data *in situ*, as they represent a more direct measurement of ES delivery (Boeraeve et al., 2020a).

To answer the sub-question of RQ1, the methods described above were also applied for reference units (field, woodland), where applicable. In addition, my findings will also be compared with reference values reported in the literature across relevant scientific disciplines. This comparative analysis with secondary data will provide a broader interdisciplinary context (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Research approach to answer the sub-question of RQ1.

To answer RQ2, an integrated assessment of permaculture’s contributions will be analysed by a comparative, theory-informed approach, situated within sustainability science. This method enables the integration of measured data with insights from interdisciplinary literature to evaluate the potential contributions of permaculture ecosystems to multifunctionality and resilience (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Approach to answering research question 2 (RQ2).

2.2. Research sites

2.2.2. Selection and eligibility

At the time this research began, there were no public or commercial permaculture sites in Czechia, so study sites were selected from among privately owned farms and gardens. Small properties, farmed by private owners for subsistence rather than commercial purposes, have been central to permaculture as an agroecosystem from the beginning anyway (Mollison & Holmgren, 1978). A multistage, emergent purposeful sampling strategy was employed (Patton, 2002) and two Belgian professional farms were later added to the sample to broaden the scope. Prior to contacting any sites, selection criteria were defined drawing on my personal knowledge of the Czech permaculture movement, informed by a Permaculture Design Certificate (PDC) training I completed in 2009. These criteria included:

- **Age of the farm:** the farm must have been in existence for at least five years, i.e. it must have been established no later than 2013
- **Farm size:** The size of the farm must be at least 1 ha
- **Food self-provisioning:** The owners aimed at food self-provisioning and/or self-sustenance when the farm was established
- **Permaculture training:** The owner must have completed the PDC at some point in the past (self-attestation by the interviewee)

Most of these criteria were important for the quantitative part of the research, especially the age and size of the farm. Consequently, no other criteria were included to allow for more farms and respondents in the study. The minimum farm size criterion of one hectare was based on the widely accepted notion that this size ensures the self-sufficiency for a family within the Czech permaculture movement (Kolářová, 2020) and is also considered economically viable for commercial farming (Sklenicka, 2016). The requirement for food self-provisioning and/or self-sustenance served as a precautionary measure to ensure that selected permaculture projects primarily focused on food production rather than education, with owners aiming to grow as much food as possible.

Since I knew that management practices may differ from site to site, but that the expected benefits are expected to be the same (McLennon et al., 2021, Henfrey, 2018) and

that the interpretation and application of permaculture theory among independent adopters is consistent (Hirschfeld & Van Acker, 2020), I decided not to base the selection criteria on controlling or checking the management practices as part of the eligibility process. The criterion related to PDC training was later dropped in order to include a broader range of sites and participants, as PDC courses can vary considerably between instructors (Grunewald et al., 2020). Self-proclamation of designing and managing land according to permaculture principles was used as the basis for selecting one site (Reiff et al., 2025).

Using the Czech National Permaculture Association Permakultura (CS) website³, a list of *demonstration permaculture sites* was compiled meeting the selection criteria. Not many were at least 5 years. Selected sites were contacted via email, providing details about the study, including its duration, the frequency of farm visits, the quantitative ecological measurements that would be conducted, and the focus of the qualitative interviews. One site was also recruited in person at the Czech Permaculture Conference in 2018. Later, three farms in Belgium were added through an emergent snow-ball sampling method (Merriam & Tisdell, 2015) during a study stay there that involved a cooperation with a researcher on micro farms production. The Belgian farms were commercial farms making them particularly interesting and enriching the study group. However, one of the three Belgian farms had later to be excluded from the study, because it identified itself as an agroecological farm rather than a permaculture farm.

With regard to the qualitative part of the research, it is necessary to note that recruiting private permaculture farms for a comprehensive study was rather challenging. It necessitates multiple visits to the farm or garden, which also serves as the interviewees' home. As a result, farm owners often have to accept that the researcher becomes a partial witness to their daily lives (Merriam & Tisdell, 2015) Therefore, it was beneficial that I had permaculture training and was familiar with some of the study sites from previous research.

³ <https://www.permakulturacs.cz/projekty/>, retrieved April 20th, 2024

2.2.3. Location and characteristics of research sites

Altogether, eight eligible permaculture research sites were recruited. Six in Czechia and two in Belgium. All of them were located in rural areas while one site in Belgium fell under ‘towns and suburbs’⁴. Most of municipalities where the sites were located had less than 2000 inhabitants, only one was in a municipality with more than 2000 inhabitants. Figures 6 and 7 show their locations in Czechia and Belgium.

Figure 6. Location of six study sites in Czechia, Scribble Maps. (2025). *Study locations*. Retrieved May 20, 2025, from <https://www.scribblemaps.com/maps/view/study-locations/3B0yCvtuVv>

⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/information-sources/maps/degree-urbanisation_en retrieved on April 12th, 2025

Figure 7. Location of two study sites in Belgium. Scribble Maps. (2025). *Study locations*. Retrieved May 20, 2025, from <https://www.scribblemaps.com/maps/view/study-locations/3B0yCvtuVv>

List of research sites is provided in Table 1. In the text below, sites are also referred to as “S” followed by the corresponding number (e.g. S1) or as ‘site 1’ etc. The table presents the municipality, year of establishment, mean elevation, size of the whole permaculture site and land use type from land registry. Since the Czech sites are private properties where people live, the exact locations are not disclosed in order to protect the privacy of participants. Two Belgian sites are publicly accessible and their location is shared in the note under the table.

Table 1 List of research sites with numbers in this study, locations, mean elevation, year of foundation and land use type.

Site number (S)	Municipality	Mean elevation (m)	Size of site (ha)	Year of foundation	Official land-use type
1	Postupice	520	2,5	2012	Fruit orchard
2	Bradlecká lhota	405	2	2012	Permanent grassland, arable land
3 ^a	Néthen	46	7	2009	Garden, arable land
4	Pístina	462	4	(1991)* 2003	Other land, permanent grassland
5	Skryje	323	1,5	(1991) 2007	Garden
6	Solanec pod Soláněm	535	6,5	2008	Permanent grassland, garden
7 ^b	Tienen	68	1,5	(1997) 2012	Garden, arable land
8	Třešť	635	1,5	2012	Garden
<p>a) 50°46'56"N 4°40'29"E b) 50°50'07"N 4°55'41"E * The year in brackets indicates when the owner began managing the land in general, while the year without brackets refers specifically to the start of permaculture management.</p>					

2.2.4. Data collection and sampling

The Czech sites were visited between June 2018 and August 2019, each site usually three to four times for the field research. A general protocol was developed to guide the chronological steps for collection of biophysical data (Appendix 1), with several types of sampling undertaken during each visit: during the first visit, soil measurements were conducted and soil samples collected. Soil erosion samplers and dataloggers were installed, and plant diversity assessed. During another visit, preferably in June, predator control was assessed and additional observational assessments were conducted including biodiversity if not done before and erosion samplers and dataloggers checked. Interviews were usually carried out during this stage. During the final visit, dataloggers were collected and any missing assessments completed. Time for taking soil samples was limited to spring and autumn, when the soil conditions are more optimal than in summer. Belgian farms were all visited multiple times during September 2019, with final retrieval of tools taking place in December of that year.

Some measurements could not be conducted successfully at all sites due to seasonal constraints. For example, predator control could not be measured in September and was therefore not carried out at the Belgian sites. Also, some dataloggers malfunctioned and failed to record data. Because only three sets of dataloggers were available, data coverage was incomplete. At S8 additional data loggers placement was conducted in 2021. These limitations are discussed further in the relating subchapters.

2.2.5. Biophysical data sampling

To provide an in-depth analysis of permaculture systems, several biophysical measurements were selected to capture multiple ecosystem characteristics simultaneously (Czúcz et al., 2021; Robertson et al., 2014). Ecosystem characteristics are specific features of ecosystems that can be measured or observed and described by variables (Czúcz et al., 2021) and play a decisive role for the ecosystem's ability to provide ES (Vári et al., 2022). The choice of variables (quantitative metrics) was guided by the research questions, typical configuration of permaculture ecosystems and commonly assessed characteristics in cropland and grassland research (Bank et al., 2025).

2.2.5.1. Sampling places / areas at research sites

At every research site, there were **four sampling places / areas in total**. Two types of ecosystems were selected within permaculture. These correspond to the two distinct clusters identified by Hirschfeld and Van Acker (2020) and relate to the concept of permaculture “zoning”, which primarily indicates the distance from the house:

- Vegetable polyculture bed
- Edible forest

Vegetable polyculture beds, often referred to as mixed beds, are areas for growing annual vegetables in polycultures, are areas for growing annual vegetables in polycultures. These beds usually occupy only a small proportion of the total permaculture area—typically a few dozen to several hundred square metres and are located close to the house, consistent with permaculture zoning. Figure 8 shows such a vegetable bed at S8.

Figure 8. Example of a polyculture bed at S8.

The edible forest, sometimes referred to as a “food forest” or orchard-garden (Mollison & Holmgren, 1978), is a three-storey ecosystem inspired by natural forests, where all three layers (ground/herbaceous, shrub, and tree layer) are intentionally designed and maintained (Figure 9a and 9b). Agriculturally, it usually represents permanent grasslands together with orchards, with the distinction that particular emphasis is placed on the shrub layer, which provides habitats for birds, insects, and other species. The shrub layer may form the boundary of the edible forest, but more often it appears in a mosaic with the tree layer, acting as a fast-growing pioneer element. This role is especially important when permaculture is established on land previously used for other purposes, such as conventional arable fields or grasslands, where natural successional processes are intentionally applied (Mollison & Holmgren, 1978).

Figure 9. Examples of edible forest. (a) Young forest at S1. A more developed edible forest at S8.

Two other ecosystems (sampling places / areas) were selected as reference units against which measured values of a variable can be meaningfully compared.

- a forest
- a conventional agricultural field

These two sampling places were usually not part of the permaculture site, but were located nearby. Their selection (first on map then in situ) was guided by their soil type,

which should have been the same as of the permaculture sampling places. Reference sites consisted of either long-established forests or conventional agricultural fields. Management practices, ownership and land-use history were not considered.

Soil comparability was ensured using national agricultural soil classification maps in Czechia and Belgium (VÚMOP, 2018.; Service public de Wallonie, 2019.; Databank Ondergrond Vlaanderen, 2019), with particular attention to soil texture due to its role in water retention. Since these maps only cover agricultural land, woodland and other cadastral units could not be checked beforehand; therefore, a hand-texture soil test was also applied to confirm soil similarity. In Czech fields, the agronomist responsible for management of the field was consulted to obtain access for measurements. While soil sampling from conventional fields was straightforward, maintaining erosion sampler or dataloggers over time proved difficult because of mistrust and theft. Further details are given in section 2.2.5. Table 2 summarizes sampling places and how they are addressed further in text. Soil types according to soil classification maps are presented in Table 3.

Table 2. Sampling places / areas at each research site and their description used in this study

Sampling place / area (ecosystem)	Name of sampling place in study
Vegetable polyculture bed	Bed
Edible forest (herb + shrubs + trees)	Edible forest
Woodland	Woodland
Conventional agricultural field	Field

Note: I use the term ‘sampling place’ and ‘sampling area’ complementary. In cases where data sampling was spread out more across one of these four sampling places, ‘area’ appears more appropriate.

Table 3. Types of soil at sampling places according to classification maps

Research site	Sampling place	Soil type
S1	Bed	7.29.14
S1	Edible forest	7.29.41
S1	Field	7.29.14
S1	Woodland	7.29.14 (?)
S2	Bed	7.28.41
S2	Edible forest	7.28.41
S2	Field	7.20.21
S2	Woodland	7.28.41
S3	Bed	Abp0_1
S3	Edible forest	Abp0_1
S3	Field	Abp0_1
S3	Woodland	AbB/SAF/Aba1
S4	Bed	7.64.01
S4	Edible forest	7.67.01
S4	Field	7.32.11/7.52.01
S4	Woodland	N/A
S5	Bed	4.48.14/4.22.13/4.27.57
S5	Edible forest	4.22.13
S5	Field	4.37.56
S5	Woodland	N/A
S6	Bed	8.35.54
S6	Edible forest	8.35.54
S6	Field	6.48.11
S6	Woodland	8.35.54?
S7	Bed	Pap
S7	Edible forest	UDx
S7	Field	UDx/Aba0
S7	Woodland	U-L-S
S8	Bed	7.29.44
S8	Edible forest	7.29.44
S8	Field	7.29.44

S8	Woodland	7.29.44
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2.2.5.2. Abiotic ecosystem variables measured in situ

- water infiltration rate
- soil texture
- wind erosion
- temperature
- habitat diversity

Water infiltration rate

Water infiltration is the process of water entering and moving downward through the soil profile. The infiltration rate (IR) represents the rate at which the soil surface absorbs water; when this capacity is exceeded, water accumulates or runs off (Assouline, 2013), potentially contributing to flooding. It is determined by inherent properties such as soil texture, as well as dynamic factors including antecedent soil moisture. In this study, IR was expressed in litres per second per square metre (L/s/m²).

I measured IR once at every sampling place using a self-made double-ring infiltrometer (DRI), inspired by commercial DRI of Eijkelkamp company. Although this technique has limitations (Gupta et al., 1994), it is widely regarded as a reliable method for in situ measuring (Fatehnia et al., 2016). The DRI was constructed from zinc sheet and designed for handling by one person. The outer ring had a diameter of 30 cm, the inner ring 15 cm, and both rings were 20 cm high. The outer ring buffered lateral water movement, ensuring that infiltration measured in the inner ring reflected primarily vertical flow.

First, any loose soil cover was removed from the chosen spot so that soil became visible. Ideally, I measured at spots between plants or on bare soil—in edible forests that was not possible since the plant cover was dense. In these cases, the grass was cut short and the surface cleared manually with a hand or spade. Then both rings were inserted 5 cm into the ground using a wooden beam and a rubber mallet (Figure 10).

Figure 10. Infiltration rate measurement prepared. Sampling place: edible forest.

A sponge was placed inside the outer ring and water was poured through it from a watering can until it reached the 5 cm mark on the ruler. Then, the sponge was placed into the inner ring and water was poured till 5 cm was reached there as well. At that point the measurement began. When the water in the inner ring had infiltrated, the time was noted using a pocket timer (Figure 11).

Figure 11. Infiltration rate measurement with double ring infiltrometer and timer running: a=field, b=woodland, c=bed.

This was repeated until infiltration rate stabilised. The duration of each run was recorded in seconds, and the mean infiltration time was then calculated from these measurements. The results were then normalised to the 5 cm water column used in all measurements according to the formula

$$IR = 50/t,$$

where IR is the infiltration rate in $L/s/m^2$, t is the recorded infiltration time in seconds, 50 represents the equivalent of a 5 cm water column applied over $1 m^2$ (i.e. $50 L/m^2$). This yielded the mean infiltration rate (IR) for each sampling place in $L/s/m^2$.

Soil texture

Soil texture is an abiotic ecosystem variable defined by the proportions of sand, silt and clay in soils. As an inherent property determined by parent material and geological processes, soil texture is not altered by land use or management. However, it strongly influences physical and chemical properties of soil and therefore the ecological processes such as water retention (Pan et al., 2018) measured in this study. Knowledge of soil texture is essential for comparing different ecosystems without overlooking basic trends.

Soil texture was estimated using a manual hand soil test (HST) at three depths in each of the 32 sampling places. After infiltration measurements were completed, the double rings were removed and the site left for 12 hours. In the area where the inner ring had been placed, first soil samples were taken at three depths (0–5 cm, 10–15 cm and 25–30 cm) using the Kopecky ring and corresponding kit (Pospíšilová & Vlček, 2016) for later laboratory measurements. Here, soil samples for the HST were taken at the same depths with a spade and soil texture was estimated using the manipulative hand test (Figure 12 and 13).

- Take a handful of soil and wet it so that it begins to stick together, but without sticking to your hand;

A

- Roll the soil sample into a ball about 3 cm in diameter;

B

- Put the ball down...

C

- If it falls apart, it is **sand**;
- If it sticks together, go on to the next step.
- Roll the ball into a sausage shape, 6-7 cm long ...

D

- If it does not remain in this form, it is **loamy sand**;
- If it remains in this shape, go on to the next step.
- Continue to roll the sausage until it reaches 15-16 cm long

E

- If it does not remain in this shape, it is **sandy loam**;
- If it remains in this shape, go on to the next step.
- Try to bend the sausage into a half circle ...

F

- If you cannot, it is **loam**;
- If you can, go on to the next step.
- Continue to bend the sausage to form a full circle ...
- If you cannot, it is **heavy loam**;
- If you can, with slight cracks in the sausage, it is **light clay**;
- If you can, with no cracks in the sausage, it is **clay**.

G

Figure 12. The hand manipulative test. Reproduced from Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), *Simple Methods for Aquaculture – Soil* (n.d.).

Figure 13. Manipulative hand soil test in practice: (a) ball, (b) sausage shape, (c) full circle. Result: light clay soil texture.

The results were mostly evaluated directly in the field. Problematic samples were evaluated later in lab (by HST). In 2019, a different hand soil test (HST) was used, as the original version had omitted parts of the soil texture triangle and proved less detailed (Figure 14).

Figure 14. Hand soil texture test (adapted from a flow chart by Steve Thien, 1979). Source: Cornell University, Soil Architecture course materials.

In the second research year, the new HST was used, but results from the original test were also recorded to maintain comparability across years. Results of HST were also cross-checked with agricultural soil maps from both countries in cases where I was uncertain about the HST outcome, since these maps also include the drainage class of the

soils (VÚMOP, 2018.; Service public de Wallonie, 2019.; Databank Ondergrond Vlaanderen, 2019).

Wind erosion

Soil erosion by wind is a serious problem worldwide. The erosion of surface soil by wind renders the soil less productive by removing the most fertile part of the soil, namely, the clays and organic matter. Agriculture practices can lead to soil erosion or prevent it (Power, 2010). Permanent vegetation and forests show better erosion protection (Milazzo et al., 2023). To measure wind-driven soil erosion, the Modified Wilson and Cooke (MWAC) sediment catcher is the second most widely used device (Van Donk & Skidmore, 2001). The MWAC collects airborne sediment at heights ranging from 0.05 to 1.00 m into bottles with an inlet and an outlet, and is equipped with a vane to ensure that the inlet always faces the wind. It has been shown to be most effective close to the ground, particularly up to 0.26 m (Sterk & Raats, 1996).

A compact mechanical erosion collector was developed, inspired by the MWAC design, that was lightweight, easy to transport, and simple to install. The sampler consisted of a horizontal stainless-steel arm fitted with a triangular vane at one end and a 1-litre laboratory plastic bottle with two openings at the other, designed to capture airborne particles. The arm rotated smoothly on a bearing attached to the vertical support, allowing the vane to align the inlet with the wind. The design of the sampler is illustrated in Figure 15.

Figure 15. Drawing of the soil erosion sampler with proportions.

At each research site, a maximum of three samplers could be installed, as the devices were custom-built for this study and the budget was limited. In total, nine erosion samplers were available, allowing three soil samples to be collected per site. Sampling periods were adjusted accordingly. The samplers were deployed during periods when biomass changes were expected due to the growing season, such as spring–summer or summer–autumn (Webb et al., 2016). Each sampler was typically left in place for about three months. Placement at sampling places (the bed, edible forest, field or woodland) varied between sites. This inconsistency was largely due to access issues: the control fields were usually not owned by research participants, and permission had to be obtained from the agronomist managing the farm. Where access could not be secured, samplers

were not placed in fields to avoid the risk of loss. This risk nevertheless materialised at S4, despite the fact that the permaculture site owner also owned the adjacent organic field. Similar difficulties arose in some woodlands, where samplers were likely disturbed by animals.

The samplers were installed in the soil via the mast, with bottle inlets positioned approximately 50 cm above the ground at the start of the study. For the farms studied in the second year, this height was adjusted to about 28 cm. Figure 16 shows an erosion sampler installed at S2 in a conventional field.

Figure 16. Erosion sampler installed at S2 (conventional field).

Air temperature

To assess the ability of permaculture to regulate climate at the local (micro) level, I used data loggers Testo 174 Logger. Each data logger was attached to a stick 30 cm above the ground or to a tree where possible. Because I had only had nine devices in total, my aim was to record three sampling places at each research site, which meant that three sites could be studied at the same time: one on permaculture, one in woodland, and one in a conventional field. Woodland and field sampling places were problematic due to circumstances similar to those described above, but in most cases, it worked and they remained there for three months, ideally covering the hottest period of the year (June–September). These loggers measured temperature only and recorded it every three hours. See Figure 17 for an illustration.

Figure 17. Data logger at S4 (forest sampling place).

After the first year of measurements, most of the data loggers stopped working. New devices were then acquired for subsequent measurements on the remaining permaculture sites. Measurements at all three sampling places at S8 had to be repeated in 2021. The new loggers used from 2019 onward were DS102. They were calibrated against a professionally calibrated thermometer. Temperature was measured in °C, with records taken every hour, which proved more practical for later comparison. See Figure 18 for the newer data logger and Table 4 for the summary of recorded sampling sites.

Figure 18. Newer data logger at S7 (sampling place: bed).

Table 4. Temperature measurements at research sites. 1 = successful recording; 0 = recording attempted but failed; N/A = sampling place not used.

Site	Bed	Edible forest	Wood-land	Field
S1	1	1	1	N/A
S2	1	N/A	0	1
S3	1	N	1	1
S4	1	N/A	1	1
S5	1	N/A	1	1
S6	1	1	1	N/A
S7	1	1	1	N/A
S8	1	1	1	0

After the measurement period at each farm, the data loggers were collected and the data downloaded. Considerable adjustment was required in Excel, particularly to format the tables, improve their usability for analysis, and ensure comparability between the two types of data loggers. In the subsequent analysis, I examine maximum temperatures and climate stability at each sampling place.

Habitat diversity

Habitat diversity at each farm was assessed through a qualitative field inventory: I visually recorded the presence of diverse structural elements (e.g., orchards, raised beds, pastures, water bodies, shrub thickets, etc.) and later added information from pictures taken at the sites. This was then compiled into a site-by-feature presence–absence table. Although this approach is approximate, presence–absence assessments are well-established in ecological studies for monitoring diversity and compositional heterogeneity (Ståhl et al., 2020). This method provides an approximate but comparable estimate of structural diversity, acknowledging that some elements may have been overlooked.

2.2.5.3. Abiotic ecosystem variables measured in laboratory

- water field capacity
- aggregate water stability

- soil organic carbon content
- soil nutrient content

Water field capacity

Water field capacity (WFC) is the nearly constant soil water content after gravitational drainage has slowed after it had been saturated by rain or irrigation, expressed as a percentage. It is widely used as an operational indicator of plant-available water and is closely linked to yields (Kirkham, 2005; Weil & Brady, 2017).

The sampling procedure followed the IR measurements. Using the same sampling places, I took advantage of the fact that the soil had already been saturated during the infiltration measurements (Figure 19a). After waiting 12 hours, I collected soil samples from the same spots (the double rings having been removed after the IR measurement on the previous day). To ensure consistent volume (100 cm³), samples were taken with a Kopecky ring at depths of 0–5 cm, 10–15 cm, and 25–30 cm (Figure 19b). For each sampling place, three soil samples were collected, giving 12 per research site and 96 in total.

Figure 19. Saturated sampling spot for WFC soil sampling (a) and collection of samples with a Kopecky ring at three depths (b).

In the laboratory, the samples were first weighed, then dried in an oven at 105 °C (Pospíšilová & Vlček, 2016) for 5 hours (Figure 20), cooled, and weighed again. Gravimetric water content was calculated as the difference between wet and dry weights, a standard method in soil science (Rasheed et al., 2022; Weil & Brady, 2017). This

procedure provided an operational estimate of WFC, reflecting the water content remaining after gravitational water had largely drained.

Figure 20. Soil samples from one sampling place (depths 5-15-25 cm) before drying.

Aggregate water stability

Soil aggregation refers to the formation of aggregates through the binding of sand, silt, and clay particles with organic and inorganic materials. These aggregates vary in size and are separated by pores. Aggregate water stability (AWS) is the ability of these aggregates to remain intact under stress, and it is a widely recognised indicator of good soil structure, soil quality, and soil erodibility (Amézqueta, 1999).

To obtain aggregates for stability measurements, dried soil samples were sieved through a 2 mm mesh. Material retained on the sieve was weighed and recorded as the proportion of macro-aggregates (>2 mm) (Figure 21a, b, c), which are typically bound by fine roots and fungal hyphae and are most responsive to disturbance and rainfall (Six et al., 2004). From each sample, five macro-aggregates of >5 mm diameter were selected where

possible (Figure 21d) and stored separately. In total, 96 samples were prepared with about 5 pieces of aggregates each (480 in total). Laboratory measurements were delayed for over two years due to the Covid-19 restrictions in 2020–2021 and limited access to facilities.

The experimental procedure followed the classical water-drop test which simulates slow soil wetting by gentle rainfall and discriminates more effectively among unstable soils than rapid wetting (Amézketa, 1999; Jimba & Lowery, 2010). Including raindrop impact is important, as most aggregate breakdown in the field is caused by both wetting and drop impact (Six et al., 2004). Unlike some earlier protocols that pre-moisten aggregates to a defined water potential before testing (Imeson & Vis, 1984), I examined air-dry aggregates to simulate the effect of initial rainfall on dry soil, a condition relevant to erosion processes. A modified *Splash Art Kit* tool was used to provide digital control of droplet size (Figure 22).

Water droplets of 0.182 g were released from a height of 32 cm onto a macro-aggregate (>5 mm) placed on a 1.25 mm sieve, and the number of drops required for disintegration was recorded. An aggregate was considered disintegrated when it broke into smaller pieces that maintained a stable size of approximately 4 mm or less. This threshold was chosen under the assumption that such particles are sufficiently small to be transported by water erosion. To avoid unrealistic rainfall equivalents, a maximum of 2,000 drops was applied. From each sampling place and soil depth, three aggregates were tested and the number of drops required for disintegration was averaged.

Figure 21. Sieving the soil sample through a 2mm sieve (a), microaggregates under the sieve (b), weighing the macro-aggregates >2mm (c), macro-aggregates before selecting 5 of them (d).

Figure 22. Breakdown of soil aggregates using the Splash Art Kit tool, with detail of an aggregate on the sieve.

Soil organic carbon content

Soil organic carbon (SOC), as the main component of soil organic matter, supports nutrient cycling, enhances soil structure and stability and increases water retention capacity. It also harbours microorganisms responsible for decomposition and is therefore one of mostly studied chemical characteristics of agroecosystems and grasslands (Bank et al., 2025).

Three soil samples were collected from randomly selected spots within each of the four sampling places. Samples were taken from the 0–5 cm depth using a Kopecky ring and combined in sealed plastic bags. I focused on this surface layer because SOC concentrations are highest in the uppermost soils and are most responsive to management and disturbance (Lorenz & Lal, 2005; Poeplau & Don, 2013). In the laboratory, the

samples were dried at 40 °C and then manually crushed in a mortar to obtain the <2 mm soil fraction.

SOC concentration was determined by dry combustion using an elemental analyser (ISO: 1995), expressed as a percentage of dry mass.

Soil nutrient content

The macronutrients available in the upper soil layer (0-5 cm) were analysed: Calcium (Ca), magnesium (Mg), and potassium (K). They were extracted using the Mehlich III reagent and quantified by inductively coupled plasma–optical emission spectrometry (ICP–OES). Mehlich III is widely used in soil testing and is the standard method applied in the Czech soil testing scheme (Čermák et al., 2019; Zbíral, 2016). Analyses were performed in a certified laboratory following an accredited procedure (Central Laboratory Zbraslav, 2018). Phosphorus (P) was measured with a UV–Vis Genesys 10 spectrophotometer (Thermo Scientific). Results are expressed in mg/kg of dry soil.

2.2.5.4. Biotic ecosystem variables in situ

- predator rate
- plant species richness
- ground cover

Predation rate

Pest control through natural enemies is an important ecological process associated with diversified landscapes and biodiversity. In complex landscapes, populations of natural enemies are typically higher and pest pressure lower than in simplified landscapes. Such increased natural enemy activity is often linked to herbaceous and forested habitats, as well as to structurally diverse, patchy landscapes (Bianchi et al., 2006).

To assess pest control, I used aphids as indicator organisms. Due to their life cycle, the test could only be conducted in spring and was therefore carried out only on six Czech farms. Three species of aphids from Katz Biotech AG were used: *Aphis fabae*, which lives

on beans and vegetables, and a mixed group of *Rhopalosiphum padi* and *Sitobion avenae*, which are common cereal pests. Colonies were perpetuated under laboratory conditions for approximately two months in spring 2019 to prepare for the experiment.

Sampling was performed in two sampling areas: (i) the permaculture system (vegetable garden plus food forest) and (ii) a conventional field as a control. The control unit 'forest' was excluded from the predation-rate assessment, as the aphid species used are not forest-associated. Forest-associated aphids, while present in natural woodlands, are not available as standardised laboratory species and cannot be sourced commercially. Aphids were glued onto small cards ('bite sticks') with a removable adhesive (three aphids per card), as in Boeraeve et al. (2020) and used in their respective sampling areas (*Rhopalosiphum padi* on permaculture and *Rhopalosiphum padi* and *Sitobion avenae* in the field). I used the 'predation protocol' as Bertrand et. al (Bertrand et al., 2016). Ten cards (30 aphids) were randomly distributed in each sampling area with a minimum distance of 10 m between cards and at least 25 m from the area borders. The cards were placed upside down with aphids facing the ground and left in situ for 24 hours. Cards were then collected and remaining aphids counted (Appendix II). Predation rate was calculated as the proportion of disappeared aphids relative to the initial number per card and subsequently expressed on a scale ranging from low to high. The process is illustrated in Figure 23.

Figure 23. Experimental setup for measuring predation rate: (a) three aphids glued onto a bite stick; (b) bite stick placed in a bed at site S4 and marked with a red band; (c) bite stick placed in a field at site S1, marked with a red band; (d) example of a collected bite stick.

Plant species richness

To gain at least a preliminary indication of how permaculture management supports agrobiological diversity, I measured plant species richness (the number of different species present) across the four different sampling areas. Altieri (Altieri, 1999a) emphasises that the species richness of traditional agroecosystems can be comparable to that of many natural systems, making it an important variable to assess. I usually used a vicinity of the sampling spots of the previously described measurements and sampling. The exact

number of sampling plots per sampling area was adjusted according to the structural heterogeneity of each ecosystem type, resulting in 1–3 plots per area:

- Bed: 3 plots
- Edible forest: 1–2 plots depending on heterogeneity
- Woodland: 3 plots
- Field: 1-3 plots depending on heterogeneity

This approach corresponds to stratified sampling, where plots are distributed across areas with relatively homogeneous properties (habitat stratification). In homogeneous areas, a single spot was sufficient, while in heterogeneous areas multiple spots were used to capture variability. Within each stratum, quadrats were placed randomly to avoid observer bias. This combination of stratification and random placement ensured that vegetation diversity was represented while still allowing for statistical evaluation (Kent, 2012).

Plant species richness was surveyed in a non-destructive way. At place, I recorded the number of observed plant species within a 0,41 m² plot, marked by a portable circular plastic frame with a diameter of 72 cm that was convenient for my purposes and the type of vegetation type (Ferris-Kaan & Patterson, 1999) (Figure 24). The number of unique species was recorded and an average was made according to the number of plots.

Figure 24. Three sampling spots in one sampling area: bed at S3

Although extrapolation to 1 m² is widely applied in studies of herbaceous species composition and cover-abundance (Barnett et al., 2019), I decided against using it here. The assumption of linearity may not hold in vegetable beds, fields, or woodlands, and would therefore only be appropriate for the edible forest. For this thesis, I therefore report averages based on the 0,41 m² plots.

Ground cover

Ground cover is beneficial for regulating ES provision and soil quality (Kremen & Miles, 2012; Six et al., 2002). When soil is left uncovered, it is more susceptible to various unfavourable processes such as erosion, nutrient loss, decrease in aggregate stability, soil organic carbon and biological activity, all of which can be associated with lower and less stable yields (Derpsch et al., 2010; Luján Soto et al., 2021).

While visual estimates are generally considered less precise, they are appropriate when the expected changes are large and only approximate values are required. As visual estimates can be subject to observer bias, consistency is ensured by having the same observer conduct all cover assessments, which reduces error across successive samplings (Ferris-Kaan & Patterson, 1999)

In this study, ground cover was defined as the proportion of the soil surface not obscured by vegetation (growing or decaying) or mulch when viewed from above, corresponding to the vertical projection of vegetation onto a horizontal ground surface. Cover was assessed within a 0.41 m² circular quadrat (Ø 72 cm) marked by a plastic frame, and visually estimated by the observer from standing height. Observations were carried out between June and September at each site. No technical instruments were used; measurements represent visual estimates of the percentage of bare ground within the observed area.

At each sampling area (bed, edible forest, woodland, field), sampling spots were chosen randomly, with the intention of capturing a representative spot. In cases where the area appeared visually homogeneous, meaning that soil cover did not vary substantially, a single spot was assessed. Where heterogeneity in soil cover was evident, up to three spots were measured within the area and the results averaged.

For the final analysis, some results were briefly cross-checked using an AI tool (ChatGPT) to validate the quality of field observations. This approach was particularly useful in cases where the distinction between plants and bare soil was clear, allowing pixel-based calculations to provide more accurate percentages than visual estimation. However, in other situations the method proved less reliable, as it was unable to distinguish between mulch and soil or to detect bare soil beneath dense vegetation.

2.2.5.5. Summary of measured variables

To synthesise the above-described measurements and assessments, Table 5 provides an overview of the variables considered in this study together with the ecosystem characteristics to which they relate. The table highlights not only the specific variables measured or assessed, but also their broader links to ecosystem characteristics, thereby emphasising the wide scope of this research and its aim to capture as many relevant dimensions of permaculture ecosystems as possible in relation to the provision of ES. The categorisation of ecosystem characteristics follows Czucz et al. (2021) and Bank et al. (2025).

Table 5. List of biophysical measurements and their variables. The right column indicates the ecosystem characteristics and processes to which the variables are related. Colour coding: blue = physical, yellow = chemical, brown = structural, light blue = functional, pink = compositional, and grey = landscape state characteristics.

Variable	Unit	Number of samples / sampling spots	Related ecosystem characteristics / processes
Infiltration rate (IR)	L/sec/m ²	32	Soil water regime
Water field capacity (WFC)	%	96	Soil water regime
Soil aggregate stability	g g ⁻¹	96	Soil stability
Wind erosion	g/t	19	Soil stability
Soil texture	Scale 1-3	96	Soil structure
Content of nutrients: P, Ca, Mg, K	%	32	Soil nutrient status
Carbon content	%	32	Soil organic matter
Bare soil	%	58	Ground cover
Temperature	°C,	23	Microclimate
Predation rate	%	12	Biotic interaction
Species richness	Number of species	55	Plants community
Habitat diversity	Number of habitats	8	Landscape diversity

2.2.6. Qualitative data collection

2.2.6.1 Methodological conceptual framework

Based on a constructivist epistemology, which emphasises the situated and individual construction of understanding, I approached human–nature relationships as emergent from lived experience, place-based practice, and social interactions within permaculture ecosystems. To capture the broad scope of non-material benefits, I drew on multiple frameworks (Chan, Guerry, et al. 2012; Chan, Satterfield, et al. 2012; Daniel et al. 2012; Fish et al. 2016); the Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services (CICES) (Haines-Young & Potschin 2018); and the NCP framework (Díaz et al. 2018). From these, I identified ten categories of non-material benefits (Table 6), tailored to the context of permaculture. As permaculture sites function mainly as living, working spaces for food production and habitation, conventional tourism-oriented benefits were considered largely irrelevant and I prioritised the non-physical value of activities (Gould et al. 2015). Spatially, the benefits arise from productive ecosystems—farms and gardens—actively shaped and co-created by the owners or managers through permaculture practice. To support navigation across existing ES frameworks (Cheng et al., 2019), I provide corresponding categories of cultural ES and non-material NCP.

Table 6. Categories of non-material benefits (cultural ES) examined in this research, aligned with non-material NCP categories.

Non-material benefits (cultural ES)	Definition^a	Non-material NCP^b
Activity	A value entailed in various active or immersive interactions that take place in permaculture ecosystems and contribute to health and well-being of the practitioners.	Physical and psychological experiences
Aesthetics	I understand the aesthetic value as the affective and sensory impact of physical places or a visually pleasing experience, often connected to scenic beauty.	
Learning and knowledge	Intellectual engagement with permaculture ecosystems and thus their inspirational, educational, and professional development value. It involves both ecological understanding at the level of general intellectual progress but also aspects of individual development.	Learning and inspiration
Heritage	The connection between natural and semi-natural features of the environment and individual or community identity. Ecosystems, with their biophysical characteristics, artifacts, and intangible attributes, offer experiences shared across generations, fostering community interactions. This benefit can manifest in specific ecosystems, species, or individual plants.	Supporting identities
Identity	A social process, often tied to physical places and practises, that encompasses who we are, to whom we belong, and which site-based knowledge and values define us.	

Spirituality	Natural places serve as religious and philosophical resources, inspiring spiritual thoughts and experiences—such as awe, reverence, humility, and the sublime in the presence of greater forces. They engage human imagination, animating the physical world in intangible ways and encompass living systems that hold symbolic meaning for humans.	
Sense of place	The non-material appreciation of a location, shaped by personal or community experiences, and a deep attachment to its meaningful physical features.	
Existence	The appreciation of the intrinsic value of other non-human organisms and natural objects regardless of the future experiences associated with them.	
Bequest	The value participants see in the permaculture ecosystem that benefits future generations.	Maintenance of options
<p>^a Definitions are my adaptations on multiple sources (e. g. (Chan, Guerry, et al. 2012; Chan, Satterfield, et al. 2012; Daniel et al. 2012; Fish et al. 2016; Haines-Young and Potschin 2018; Ryfield et al. 2019).</p> <p>^b Categories are listed in the standard NCP order (right column).</p>		

2.2.6.1. Interviews

To capture the non-material benefits arising from these relationships, qualitative methods are most suitable (Chan, Guerry, et al., 2012; Dendoncker et al., 2018; Fish et al., 2016; Himes et al., 2024), particularly when contextualised within place (Fish et al., 2016). A phenomenological approach was therefore adopted, offering an appropriate lens for investigating benefits that are intangible, interpretive, and socially mediated (Fish et al., 2016).

Among qualitative approaches, interviews are the most common method for exploring non-material ecosystem services, as they provide deeper insight into how and why people value them (Cheng et al., 2019). Between January and September 2019, I conducted 11 semi-structured, face-to-face interviews. In Czechia, participants were individual landowners of the previously described research sites, in some cases it was a couple. S4 was a retired agricultural business managing about 20 hectares, of which only 4 ha follow permaculture principles; the other Czech sites were not professional. In Belgium, three participants from professional, market-oriented farms (S3, S7) were interviewed: a gardener-employee, a cooperative economic team member and permaculture teacher, and a farm manager-gardener on a family-run site. Table 7 summarises participant information and interviewees' IDs used later in the results.

Table 7. Interview participant characteristics relevant to the study.

Respondent ID (F=female, M=male)	Age	Role in project	Works there physically	PDC training	Prior professional farming/gardening experience
F1	45	Owner	Part-time	N	Y
M1	44	Owner	Part-time	N	Y
F2	40	Owner	Part-time	Y	N
M3	56	Project member (employed)	No	Y	N
M33	35	Gardener (employed)	Yes	N	Y
M4	65	Owner	Yes	N	Y
F5	44	Owner	Yes	Y	N
F6	46	Owner	Part-time	Y	N
M7	40	Manager /gardener (employed)	Yes	Y	Y
M8	36	Owner	Part-time	Y	N
F8	35	Owner	Part-time	N	N

Note: Y=yes, N=no.

Interviews were conducted in Czech (Czechia) and English (Belgium), with a gender-balanced sample of six men and five women. Over half of participants had the PDC training. No pilots were done; the interview protocol (*Appendix III*) was deemed sufficient and slightly refined after two interviews. Participants were informed that participation was voluntary, and that interviews would be recorded and anonymised, with age as the only personal data collected. Interviews lasted 60–80 minutes and focused on three topics: participants' understanding of permaculture; the land and its benefits, and the structure and history of sites, where relevant. To encourage open reflection, I avoided ES terminology (Raymond et al. 2013), explaining that the aim was just to understand what permaculture-based food growing meant to them. While the primary focus was on non-material benefits, other ES groups (e.g. regulating or material) were considered if mentioned.

I applied three approaches when asking: first, I used open questions that were narrative and descriptive (Chan, Guerry, et al. 2012) and were aimed at the images and symbols the participant connected with the land. I asked about the feelings the owner has when they are on their land and what associations they have with different aspects of the land or the activities they carry out there, including the meaning of these phenomena for them. Then, the second part of the interview was organised according to the categories of benefits from cultural ES as presented in Table 5. And third, a situational narrative question closed off the interview to prompt respondents to describe how they would behave in a specific situation, facilitating a more organic list of benefits in their minds rather than relying on a predefined list, thus engaging a different cognitive process (Gould *et al.*, 2015).

The questions in the protocol did not need to be fully exhausted during the interview; instead, they served as a guiding framework. Often, responses to initial questions that encouraged deeper thinking led me to ask questions from later sections of the questionnaire, resulting in a unique interview process for each respondent.

2.2.7. Data collection for material services

To address both RQ1, and RQ2 and because the original idea of permaculture was to consciously design sustainable yet agriculturally productive ecosystems (Mollison, 1988), I also ought to examine the extent to which they are capable of producing food and other material goods.

As I knew in advance that permaculture practitioners did not keep accurate records of their harvests, I was inspired by a comparable study facing a similar lack of quantitative data (Morel et al., 2018) and developed an interview-based approach to estimate production. Interview exploring the material benefits was the second interview I did with the participants of the non-material benefits interviews. Here, usually one respondent from each study site took part, in some cases, both (if partners).

Food types were chosen according to the Czech Household Budget Survey (Dofkova et al., 2001), and pictures were used to prompt respondents to indicate whether they purchased these foods “often”, “occasionally, or “never” (Figure 25). Based on these responses, I aimed to estimate household-level production by comparing reported purchasing behaviour with the average consumption of food in Czechia as reported in the literature.

The case of one of the two Belgian farms (S7) was more straightforward. As a professional farm, they maintained records of their harvests and sales. Data from 2019 were obtained and quantified. Data from S3 could not be obtained.

Figure 25. Food categories reported by the respondent at site S5, classified according to purchasing frequency (*never buy, occasionally, often*) from the left.

2.3. Data analysis

Similarly to the methods used for data collection, the data analysis employed analytical approaches tailored to each type of data and to the respective ES they were intended to inform.

2.3.1. Material ecosystem services

Semi-quantitative data obtained from interviews were transcribed and processed in the same way as the non-material benefits (see 2.3.3.). In this case, the interviews were guided by the choice of pictures, and the analysis focused primarily on these. However, several parts of the interviews about non-material benefits also contained substantial

information on material benefits. These sections were coded and included as additional material in the analysis.

Already during the interviews at the private study sites, it became clear that yields were influenced by many factors, several of which were highly personal. As a result, yields varied from year to year and there was no 'average' or 'typical' year that could be meaningfully described. In addition, some farms (S1, S4, S5) either organised workshops on-site and used the yields for these activities, cooked with them elsewhere, or provided food for extended family members who visited regularly. For these reasons, quantifying yields according to average consumption per person per year was not possible. Therefore, I applied a semi-quantitative analysis and interpretation for the private research sites, while for one commercially operating site (S7), which provided me with records of products sold in 2019, I was able to carry out a quantitative statistical analysis.

2.3.2. Regulating ecosystem services

2.3.2.1. Adjustment of variables

Soil texture

Originally estimated soil texture span over seven categories and was therefore grouped into three simplified categories for analytical purposes: loams (1), clay loams (2) and clays (3). A modified soil texture triangle (Figure 26), designed for estimation by feel, was used (Kansas State University, n.d., adapted from King et al., 2003). Results from the three soil depths were averaged to obtain a single value for soil texture at each sampling place (Table 8) for analytical and comparison cases where only one number was needed per sampling site.

Figure 26. Modified soil texture triangle used for analysis. Reprinted from Soil texture and structure (Kansas State University, n.d.), which is adapted the figure from King et al. (2003).

Table 8. Soil texture averaged for each sampling place across sites.

Research site / Sampling place	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6	S7	S8
Bed	2	2	2	3	2	2	2	1
Edible forest	2	2	2	1	2	2	3	1
Field	2	3	2	2	1	3	3	1
Woodland	2	2	1	1	1	2	1	1

As is apparent, not all sampling sites at each one study location ultimately had the same soil texture. This could influence later results and their comparison; therefore, a coefficient will be used to standardise the baseline for other variables.

Infiltration rate

To account for inherent differences in infiltration capacity among soil textures within one study site, observed IR were normalised using published typical values. Following Hillel (1982) typical steady IR are:

- (1) Sandy and silty loams 10-20 mm/h⁻¹
- (2) Clay loams 5-10 mm/h⁻¹
- (3) Clays 1-5 mm/h⁻¹

Using the upper limits of these ranges as class references (20, 10, and 5 mm h⁻¹), I defined a ratio of 1 : 2 : 4 (loam : clay loam : clay). Observed IRs were then normalised to a common baseline by multiplying by the corresponding class-specific multiplier (loam ×1, clay loam ×2, clay ×4). Where sampling places within a site did not share the same texture, values were expressed on the lighter (coarser) soil baseline, so that within-site comparisons reflect texture-adjusted differences.

2.3.2.2. Comparative analysis

Collected biophysical data were analysed statistically in Microsoft Excel to generate site-based comparisons. For each measured variable, available values from permaculture sampling places (bed, edible forest) were compared with those from reference units (field and woodland). Sampling places were also compared across sites to capture presence of trends. Descriptive statistics (means, medians, ranges, differences) were calculated according to the case and visualised, which allowed the distribution of values to be compared between sampling places.

2.3.2.3. Statistical analysis

Statistical environment

To capture the multivariate situation of ecosystem conditions at different study sites, all analyses were conducted in **R (v. 4.x; R Core Team, Vienna, Austria)**. Linear mixed-effects models (LMMs) were fitted using the package **lme4** (Bates et al., 2015),

which implements restricted maximum likelihood (REML) estimation via the `lmer()` function. Model summaries were tidied for inference and presentation using `broom.mixed`, while formatted regression tables were exported with `sjPlot`. Narrative, APA-style summaries of model outputs were generated using the `report` package to facilitate reproducibility of textual interpretations.

Response transformations and diagnostics

For each soil indicator (Infiltration, Water Field Capacity [WFC_adjusted], Aggregate Water Stability [AWS], Soil Organic Carbon [SOC], and Bare Soil [BS]), response distributions were first inspected visually (`hist()`). Where departures from normality were evident, a log_{1p}-transformation (`log1p()`) was applied to stabilize variance and improve normality (e.g. infiltration, AWS, SOC). Residual diagnostics were conducted for each model using standard diagnostic plots (`plot()` for residuals vs. fitted values; `qqnorm()` and `qqline()` for Q–Q inspection). These procedures confirmed approximate normality and homoscedasticity of residuals across fitted models.

Model specification

For each response, two candidate models were compared:

1. **Full model** — including the fixed effects of `sample_place` (categorical factor with “Bed” as reference), soil depth (`depth_cm`, categorical with three strata: 0–5 cm, 10–15 cm, 25–30 cm), and their two-way interaction where appropriate. Site-level heterogeneity was accounted for by including `site_id` as a random intercept (`(1|site_id)`).
2. **Null model** — including only the intercept and random effect of `site_id`, representing the hypothesis of no systematic land-use or depth effect.

This approach allowed partitioning of variance attributable to fixed land-use contrasts versus background site variability.

Model selection

Model selection proceeded via a two-step approach. First, **likelihood ratio tests (LRTs)** were performed using the `anova()` function to compare the full model to its corresponding null model. This tests whether inclusion of the fixed effects significantly improved model fit. Second, **Akaike's Information Criterion (AIC)** was calculated for both models using the `AIC()` function. Models with lower AIC were considered to provide a more parsimonious description of the data, penalizing model complexity. In all cases reported, full models had substantially lower AIC values than null models, justifying the inclusion of fixed effects of `sample_place` and, where relevant, `depth_cm` and their interaction.

Inference and presentation

Point estimates of fixed effects (β coefficients), standard errors, and 95% confidence intervals were extracted using `broom.mixed::tidy()`. Regression tables were produced with `sjPlot::tab_model()`, including model fit indices (AIC, intraclass correlation coefficient [ICC], marginal and conditional R^2). For interpretability, all coefficients are presented relative to the baseline category (`Bed` at 0–5 cm depth). Textual model summaries (`report::report()`) were saved alongside regression tables, ensuring consistent reporting between narrative and visual outputs.

2.3.2.4. Variables and their relation to ecosystem services

To capture a wide array of ecosystem services and to incorporate all measured variables, the terminology of services and nature's contributions is used following both the MA (2005) and Díaz at al. (2018b). Variables will be converted to indicators to obtain results.

Table 9. Ecosystem services and their variables. Green = biodiversity, red = provisioning services, blue = regulating services.

Ecosystem service / Natures' contribution to people	Measured variable(s)
Habitat creation and maintenance	Habitat diversity
Biodiversity	Species richness
Provisioning / Material	Food yields and other material benefits
Microclimate regulation	Temperature, bare soil
Pest control / Regulation of detrimental organisms	Predation rate
Flood control / Regulation of hazards and extreme events	Infiltration rate, water field capacity, aggregate water stability, soil organic carbon
Erosion control / Protection of soils	Bare soil, soil organic carbon, aggregate water stability
Soil fertility / Formation of soils	Content of nutrients, soil organic carbon, aggregate water stability

2.3.3. Non-material benefits

The recorded interviews were transcribed verbatim using MAXQDA, a software designed for qualitative data analysis that includes an automatic transcription tool. An iterative process of deductive and inductive coding was applied (Bryman, 2016) to analyse the content. In the first round of coding two groups of codes were applied. One group of codes contained descriptive coding into categories according to the pre-selected non-material benefits. The second group emerged through exploratory coding (Saldaña, 2013) and captured various phenomena mentioned by the respondents. These codes included information about other benefits provided by the permaculture ecosystem outside the pre-selected categories – such as regulating and material benefits and services. Many of these

codes emerged directly from participants' lived experiences, and their identification was guided by a phenomenological sensitivity (Merriam & Tisdell, 2015). In the second round of coding, the initially assigned codes were revisited and refined making sure they really reflected the patterns that started to emerge in the meanings behind the stories and beliefs expressed by the respondents (Saldaña, 2013). At this point, it became evident that the data reflected respondents' values to a surprisingly wide extent—something not anticipated in the beginning. Given the phenomenological design of the interviews, a value-based analysis emerged as a natural and necessary step. This perspective provided a more holistic understanding than an analysis of benefits alone (Chan, Satterfield, et al., 2012; Gould et al., 2015).

During the analysis of each non-material benefit, I employed a mixed-method approach using the MAXQDA tool to assess the frequency of mentions among individual participants and evaluate the generality of the statements describing each phenomenon. For the theme development, key points in each coded segments were recorded, accompanied by frequency notes; and similarities were identified to extract emerging themes. The benefit descriptions were concluded with significant quotes that best represented each theme. Narratives were then constructed based on both frequency and thematic coherence, to reflect how participants experienced and interpreted the non-material benefits. For the analysis of values, I followed a similar approach. The group of assigned codes for each value was reviewed to capture the recurring narratives, from which a descriptive synthesis was developed. This stage of the analysis focused on identifying and interpreting key connections between specific benefits and values, particularly where clarification was needed for accurate interpretation. The final phase involved an iterative process of refining the descriptions and cross-checking the interpretations to ensure both analytical rigour and ease of reading.

3 Results and findings

3.1. Material ecosystem services and benefits

3.1.2. Private research sites

Here, the results obtained through qualitative methods show, that practitioners gain these material benefits they value:

- Firewood
- Clean water
- Food
- Food for sale
- Compost

Firewood is a typical product. At S4, it is never purchased, as part of the land is woodland and additional trees are integrated into the edible forest. S1, S2, S5, and S8 also secure their firewood partly through coppicing, planting hazelnut trees specifically for this purpose.

Clean water as a material benefit was mentioned by some respondents, particularly those whose sites are not connected to the municipal water supply.

As far as food self-provisioning is concerned, none of the respondents aimed to be 100% self-sufficient. However, growing food in a healthy and ecologically positive way was a key motivation for many, as discussed in more detail in Chapter 3.4. A few participants mentioned that during the growing season they did not need to purchase vegetables at all. The extent of self-provisioning often depended on family size, since vegetable production was usually managed by a single person. Two respondents estimated that around 30% of their food was self-provided and reflected on how this might be increased (for example, if both partners were actively involved in cultivation, or if all eggs from their chickens were collected). Site S4 was a bit outside-the-box in this respect: the participant had a background in organic dairy farming and pork production, and the site remains largely self-sufficient in vegetables, eggs, and pork, providing for an extended family of around ten people. At S6, the family produces their own dairy products, but with seven members, they are not fully self-sufficient in milk products and had to buy them too.

Food production, consumption and purchases were largely influenced by the diet of the respective participants. If they did not eat meat or dairy products (S1, S5), or had a healthier diet (S2, S8), **meat** was not bought at all or just occasionally. Some sites had their own **poultry** and all of them had own **eggs**, although if the family was large, they had to buy them occasionally. **Cheese** was bought by all non-vegan sites often. **Bread, grains and flour** – this group of foods varied across respondents, depending on what they ate and how they prepared their food. Four sites did not buy bread, because they baked their own—sometimes not from flour, but from grains that they first had to grind. **Grains** (wheat) are also purchased at sites where they were used to feed animals. Most sites stated that they were buying **rice** often, one just occasionally. **Millet, buckwheat and corn** was bought often by those on vegan or vegetarian diet. **Potatoes** were bought either occasionally or often by all respondents except of S4 who had their own. **Pasta** was bought by every site as well. **Plant oils** were purchased frequently across all sites. **Sweet treats** were also bought at all sites, though mostly occasionally. **Sugar** rather occasionally, at S5 malt was used instead of sugar, at S1 date paste as well. In the group of **nuts**, almonds were bought by every site, usually often, other nuts were bought variably often across sites. S8 had their own hazelnuts and did not need to buy. Sunflower **seeds** were bought by every site, pumpkin seeds just by some. Coconut and its products were bought occasionally by all. Vegan participants bought **nut cheeses or nut milk**, but also produced their own from sunflower or other seeds. **Berries** were not bought by any site in general and the same applied to **typical fruits** such as apples, pears and apricots. S2 indicated buying apples often, because their own trees were not bearing them yet. **Lettuce, spinach and herbs** were generally not bought, because the own produce was sufficient. Sometimes, especially out of the season, they were bought occasionally, however S2 bought them often, but during the growing season they were self-sufficient in them. Here it is interesting to note that four respondents mentioned eating less traditional spinach or salad substitutes as well, such as nettles, bishop's weed (*Aegopidium podagraria*) or garden orache (*Artiplex hortensis*). Traditional vegetables such as **onion, carrot, beetroot and radish** were bought more often, especially onion and carrot. Some mentioned that they rarely had their own for the whole year, except for carrots at S4. Radish was not bought by three sites at all. The family of **nightshades** that is very season dependent in

Czechia offered a varied picture. Here, every site produced enough courgettes, most of sites pumpkins and cucumbers. Tomatoes were bought often by S4, otherwise occasionally by three sites and not at all by two. Peppers were mostly bought occasionally. Also here, it was seasonal, because peppers and tomatoes cannot be stored over winter for a fresh consummation. The **brassica family** offered a varied picture too. Mostly, Brussels sprouts, cabbage, cauliflower and broccoli were bought occasionally or not at all (own produce was sufficient), except for cabbage, which three sites reported buying often. S1 was also buying cauliflower and broccoli often. **Legumes** were partly bought and partly grown too. Four sites were buying lentils often, two occasionally. S1 was buying peas occasionally but beans, lentils and soy products often. S5 was buying peas often. S4 and S8 had enough of their own peas and did not need to buy, others were buying beans and soy products occasionally. S4 was not buying soy products at all, because not eating them. Group of **exotic fruits** showed that many items were not bought at all by many sites – typically avocado, kiwi, mango and ananas, others were bought more often – mainly lemons and bananas, where half of respondents would buy them just occasionally. Although melons and other tropical fruits were grown on the study sites as well, they only yielded few pieces of fruit and therefore would have to be bought at least occasionally. **Mushrooms** were often mentioned as something provided directly by the site: so S4 did not need to buy them at all, others occasionally, S1 reported often purchases. Other products, such as tea, coffee, or olives had to be bought when consumed. Table 9 presents these results by food type for each study site.

In general, respondents frequently noted that they avoid purchasing items they can produce themselves, even if this sometimes requires waiting until a particular vegetable or fruit is in season and available in their garden. Also notable was the breadth of grown vegetables or plants that extended beyond what could be captured by the pictures leading the interview. For example, M4 reported growing around 40 types of vegetables, while M8 mentioned having about 80 edible species in total in the garden.

Table 10. Frequency of purchases of different food types.

Type of food	S1	S2	S4	S5	S6	S8
Poultry	do not buy	do not buy	N/A	do not buy	do not buy	occasionally
Meat	do not buy	occasionally	occasionally	do not buy	occasionally	occasionally
Smoked meat	do not buy	occasionally	often	do not buy	occasionally	occasionally
Fish	do not buy	occasionally	often	do not buy	occasionally	occasionally
Eggs	do not buy	do not buy	do not buy	do not buy	occasionally	do not buy
Cheese	do not buy	often	often	do not buy	often	often
Bread - toast	do not buy	do not buy	N/A	do not buy	do not buy	N/A
Bread - regular	do not buy	occasionally	often	do not buy	do not buy	often
Oats	do not buy	often	often	often	often	occasionally
Grain - wheat	do not buy	often	do not buy	often	often	occasionally
Grain - ray	do not buy	often	do not buy	often	do not buy	occasionally
Grain - gordeum	do not buy	occasionally	do not buy	occasionally	do not buy	do not buy
Rice	often	occasionally	often	often	often	often
Millet	often	occasionally	do not buy	often	do not buy	occasionally
Buckwheat	often	occasionally	do not buy	often	often	often
Corn	occasionally	often	do not buy	occasionally	occasionally	occasionally
Flour	often	do not buy	often	do not buy	often	often
Potatoes	often	occasionally	do not buy	occasionally	often	N/A
Pasta	occasionally	often	often	often	often	occasionally
Plant oils	often	often	often	often	often	often
Sweet treats	occasionally	occasionally	often	occasionally	occasionally	occasionally
Sugar	occasionally	occasionally	often	do not buy	often	occasionally
Nuts - pistacios	occasionally	occasionally	do not buy	occasionally	occasionally	do not buy
Nuts - wallnuts	do not buy	do not buy	do not buy	do not buy	often	do not buy
Nuts - hazelnuts	do not buy	occasionally	often	occasionally	often	do not buy
Nuts - arashid	do not buy	occasionally	often	occasionally	do not buy	N/A
Nuts - Cashews	occasionally	occasionally	do not buy	occasionally	occasionally	occasionally
Nuts - Almonds	often	occasionally	often	often	often	occasionally
Pumpkin seeds	often	do not buy	often	occasionally	do not buy	occasionally
Sunflower seeds	often	often	often	often	often	occasionally
Coconut	occasionally	occasionally	occasionally	occasionally	occasionally	do not buy

Nut milks	occasionally	do not buy	do not buy	occasionally	N/A	N/A
Nut cheeses	occasionally	do not buy	do not buy	N/A	N/A	N/A
Raspberries	do not buy					
Blueberries	do not buy					
Strawberries	do not buy	occasionally	do not buy	do not buy	occasionally	do not buy
Cherries	do not buy	N/A				
Gooseberry	do not buy	do not buy	do not buy	N/A	N/A	N/A
Apples	do not buy	often	do not buy	do not buy	do not buy	N/A
Plums	occasionally	do not buy				
Pears	do not buy	do not buy	occasionally	occasionally	do not buy	do not buy
Apricot	occasionally	occasionally	occasionally	occasionally	occasionally	N/A
Lettuce/salad	do not buy	often	do not buy	do not buy	occasionally	do not buy
Spinach	do not buy	occasionally	do not buy	do not buy	occasionally	do not buy
Herbs	do not buy					
Onion	often	often	often	occasionally	often	occasionally
Carrot	often	often	do not buy	often	often	occasionally
Beetroot	often	occasionally	do not buy	occasionally	occasionally	do not buy
Radish	occasionally	do not buy	do not buy	occasionally	occasionally	do not buy
Courgettes	do not buy					
Pumpkin	occasionally	do not buy	do not buy	occasionally	do not buy	do not buy
Cucumber	do not buy	do not buy	do not buy	occasionally	do not buy	do not buy
Tomatoes	occasionally	occasionally	often	occasionally	do not buy	do not buy
Aubergine	occasionally	occasionally	do not buy	occasionally	occasionally	occasionally
Peppers	occasionally	occasionally	occasionally	occasionally	occasionally	do not buy
Brussel sprouts	occasionally	occasionally	N/A	do not buy	occasionally	do not buy
Cabbage	often	often	do not buy	occasionally	often	occasionally
Cauliflower	often	occasionally	do not buy	occasionally	occasionally	occasionally
Broccoli	often	occasionally	do not buy	occasionally	occasionally	do not buy
Peas	occasionally	occasionally	do not buy	often	occasionally	do not buy
Beans	often	occasionally	N/A	occasionally	occasionally	occasionally
Lentils	often	often	often	often	occasionally	occasionally
Soybeans/tofu	often	occasionally	occasionally	occasionally	occasionally	occasionally
Avocado	often	do not buy	do not buy	occasionally	occasionally	do not buy
Kiwi	do not buy	occasionally	do not buy	do not buy	occasionally	do not buy
Oranges	occasionally	occasionally	often	do not buy	occasionally	do not buy
Mango	occasionally	occasionally	do not buy	do not buy	occasionally	do not buy
Ananas	occasionally	occasionally	do not buy	do not buy	occasionally	do not buy
Lemons	often	often	often	occasionally	occasionally	occasionally
Bananas	often	often	often	occasionally	occasionally	occasionally
Melone	occasionally	occasionally	often	N/A	occasionally	occasionally
Wine grapes	do not buy	often	do not buy	occasionally	occasionally	occasionally
Mushroom	often	occasionally	do not buy	occasionally	occasionally	occasionally
Olives	occasionally	occasionally	often	do not buy	occasionally	do not buy
Coffee	often	occasionally	often	do not buy	often	N/A
Tea	often	occasionally	often	occasionally	occasionally	N/A
Cocoa powder	often	occasionally	N/A	N/A	occasionally	N/A

Produce for sale consisted mostly of eggs, primarily from S2, who keeps around 60 chickens, and occasionally from S8. Herbs were also sold, as in the case of S6, which in the past had additionally marketed lamb meat when more sheep were kept.

Compost was mentioned several times as a material benefit that can be used as fertilizer of the garden or shrubs or trees.

3.1.3. Commercial research site

The 2019 harvest at S7 included vegetables counted by piece, vegetables measured in kilograms, small fruits, fruits, nuts, and herbs. Table 11 presents the rounded amounts for each category and count of varieties. A list of the crop varieties belonging to each category (excluding eggs) is provided below the table.

Table 11. Yields in 2019 at S7

Crop	Total	Varieties
Vegetables (pc)	1 143	22
Vegetables (kg)	1 688	52
Herbs (kg)	20	12
Small fruit (kg)	178	31
Fruit (kg)	853	39
Nuts (kg)	40	2
Subtotal (kg)	2 779	
Subtotal (pc)	5 843	
Eggs total (pc)	4 700	

Vegetables counted in pieces: Endive, celery, daylily flower, cauliflowers, Chinese cabbage, escarole, iceberg lettuce, celeriac, cucumber, curly endive (frisée), garlic shoots, spring onion, radicchio, radish, savoy cabbage, shallots, leaf celery, green lettuce, red lettuce, pointed cabbage, sweetcorn, white cabbage, red cabbage.

Vegetables counted in kg: Potatoes (Agila, Corne de Gâtes, Désiré, Rode Eersteling), Jerusalem artichoke, yellow onion, red onion, asparagus, aubergine, gherkins, blue peas, kale, butter bean, flat pole bean, round pole bean, round dwarf French bean, broccoli, courgette, peas, broad beans, garlic, horseradish, molleboon (local bean variety), New Zealand spinach, black kale (palm cabbage), yellow bell pepper, green bell pepper, mixed peppers, red bell pepper, parsnip, snow peas, chili pepper, butternut squash, green Hokkaido squash, Red Kuri squash, leek, turnip, black radish, rhubarb, beetroot, shallot, mixed lettuce, runner bean, Brussels sprouts, outdoor tomato, beefsteak tomato, cherry tomato, plum tomato, slicing tomato, lamb's lettuce, Swiss chard, winter purslane, carrots.

Herbs counted in bundles: Basil, nettle, Chinese mustard, dill, mixed herbs, chervil, coriander, herb mix, curly parsley, flat-leaf parsley, purslane, rocket (arugula).

Small fruit: Strawberries, American black currant, wild strawberry, blackberry, grapes, raspberries, yellow raspberry, autumn raspberry, red raspberry, black raspberry, Japanese wineberry, jostaberry, persimmon (kaki), cherry, kiwi, kiwiberry, sour cherry, mirabelle plum, gooseberries, medlar, mix, mulberry, muscat strawberry, red currant, pink currant, tayberry, yellow fig, purple fig, hawthorn berry, white currant, black currant.

Fruit: Apricots, apples for applesauce, apple Ananas Reinette, apple Colafuin, apple Gronsfelder Klumpke, apple Jan Steen, apple Jacques Lebel (juice), apple James Grieve, apple Tr Blanche harvest, apple Pladei, apple Précoce de Wirwignes, apple Prés. Van Dievoet, apple Radoux, apple Reine des Renettes, apple Renette Hernault, apple Ster, apple Winston, apple Winter Banana, Poncirus, quince, mirabelles, medlar, pear Beurré Hardy, pear Clapp's, pear Comtesse de Paris, pear Conférence, pear Dubbel Flip wei, pear Dubbel Flip, pear Joséphine de Malines, pear Jules d'Airolles, pear Légipont, pear Williams, pear mix juice, peach Reine des Vergers, peach Vaes, plum Anna Späth, plum Monsieur Hâtif, plum R-CI d'Oullins, plum R-CI d'Althan, plum R-CI d'Othée, plum Viktoria.

Nuts: Almonds and hazelnuts

Site S7 produced 2.779 t of vegetables, fruits and herbs per 1.5 ha and over 1,100 pieces of other vegetables in 2019. Additionally, 4700 pc of eggs were produced.

3.2. Regulating services

3.2.2. Biophysical variables

3.2.2.1. Soil variables related to flood and erosion control

Ordination analysis of soil variables across sampling places

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and Redundancy Analysis (RDA) revealed consistent patterns in the relationships between soil properties and land-use types (*sample_place*). The PCA biplot (Figure 27) showed that AWS, SOC, WFC (*WFC_adjusted*), and IR (*infiltration_adjusted*) form a positively correlated cluster, whereas Bare soil (BS) is negatively correlated with these variables. This correlation structure corresponded with a clear separation of sample places, with field sites strongly aligning with the Bare Soil vector and exhibiting higher bare soil alongside lower AWS, SOC, WFC, and IR. In contrast, bed, edible forest, and woodland sites clustered together near the positive correlation group, indicating shared soil characteristics associated with lower BS and enhanced WFC and IR. The RDA (Figure 28), constrained by *sample_place* and soil texture, confirmed this pattern, showing distinct separation of field sites from other systems and grouping of bed, edible forest, and woodland places. These results indicate that variation in key soil properties is primarily driven by differences in land-use type and soil texture, with the strongest contrast occurring between field systems and other managed or natural habitats.

Figure 27. Principal component analysis of soil related variables based on sampling place.

Figure 28. Redundancy analysis of soil related variables based on sampling place.

Individual soil variables

Models of key soil properties revealed consistent and interpretable differences among land-use types (*sample_place*), with site-level variability contributing in some cases. Bare Soil (BS) showed strong explanatory power (marginal $R^2 = 0.61$; conditional $R^2 = 0.73$), with field sites exhibiting substantially higher exposed soil cover (BS) relative to Beds ($\beta = 45.38$, $p < 0.001$), while edible forest ($\beta = -12.38$, $p = 0.009$) and woodland ($\beta = -13.75$, $p = 0.004$) showed significantly lower BS.

Infiltration rate

Descriptive analysis

Because very large percentage differences can be difficult to interpret, results are expressed both as percentages (up to 200%) and as fold changes for clarity. Figure captions (Figure 29, 30, 31) indicate the chosen texture baseline texture of the adjusted sampling places as a number: (1) loam, (2) clay loam and (3) clay.

Infiltration rate (IR) results were highly variable across sites and these differences were not caused by seasonal variations (Figures 30 and 31). Beds in permaculture sites consistently showed higher IR than fields, with differences ranging from 4,300-fold to 54%. Edible forests also tended to exceed fields, from 329-fold to 5% higher, although in one case, IR was 22% lower than in the field.

Relative to woodland, patterns were more mixed. Beds usually had higher IR, with differences ranging from 194-fold to 5%, but in some cases were moderately lower (40–76%). Edible forests ranged from 608-fold to 60% higher than woodland, but in four cases had lower IR, by 30–80%.

Five main patterns emerged: (1) in five cases both bed and edible forest had higher IR than the reference units, and within these (2) the edible forest had the highest IR three times; (3) in two cases, bed and edible forest were higher than the field but lower than woodland; (4) in one case, the bed had the highest IR of all sampling places, while the edible forest had the lowest; and (5) in another case, the bed exceeded all three other places, but the edible forest was lower than both field and woodland.

Figure 29. Infiltration rate on all research sites and at all sampling places. Values adjusted to texture class (1). One measurement per sampling place.

To rule out potential seasonal effects, I examined whether measurements taken in spring versus autumn influenced the results across different sampling places. A comparison of spring sampling (Figure 30) and autumn sampling (Figure 31) shows that seasonal timing does not appear to matter: IR rate ranges vary across places regardless of season.

Figure 30. Infiltration rate across sites measured in spring. All measurements done once.

Figure 31. Infiltration rate across sites measured in autumn. All measurements done once.

Statistical analysis

The infiltration model (Figures 32 and 33) showed substantial total explanatory power (conditional $R^2 = 0.52$). Compared with the bed, all alternative land uses exhibited significant negative effects on infiltration: field ($\beta = -0.63$, $p < 0.001$), woodland ($\beta = -0.26$, $p = 0.018$) and edible forest ($\beta = -0.23$, $p = 0.038$). These results indicate that the Bed locations had the highest infiltration rates and that the tested land uses generally reduced infiltration relative to that baseline.

Figure 32. Distribution of log-transformed infiltration values ($\log(1 + \text{Infiltration})$) across sampling places.

Figure 33. Variation in infiltration across study sites (S1–S8), shown as $\log(1 + \text{Infiltration})$ values.

Water field capacity

Descriptive analysis

Since WFC is also influenced by soil texture, a correction coefficient was applied, and all soils were adjusted to loam (indicated as (1) in the previous section) to enable comparison. The coefficient used is based on the fact that light soils have a field capacity of 15–25%, loamy soils 35–45%, and clays 45–55% (Cornell University, n.d.). When taking the upper threshold, the ratio is 1 : 1.8 : 2.2, and the results were multiplied by the coefficient according to texture class (1, 2 or 3).

Results are presented in Figures 33–35 by study site and in Figures 36–38 by sampling place.

Findings

Results show that across sites, WFC is highest in the topsoil (0-5 cm) in almost all sampling places. At four of the eight sites, beds have the highest values; twice it is the edible forest, once the field and once the woodland. With depth, WFC in beds either rises (S1, S6, S7) or declines; the decline is usually moderate except at S2 where it is ~50 %. The 25–30 cm layer in beds usually remains close to the other layers across sites, not showing a significant drop.

Edible forests show a varied picture: sometimes their WFC is higher in the topsoil than that of the beds and fields (S6, S7, S8), but it generally drops with depth, and some drops are very large (e.g., ~75 % at S8, ~40 % at S7; also pronounced at S5). In the lower layers it can be both higher and lower than the field and, with one exception (S8), where it is higher than the woodland.

Fields have a higher WFC than beds in the 0–5 cm layer at three sites, but in two of these the edible forests have a higher WFC than the fields. Their WFC stays quite stable through the depths, with only one large drop at S8 (~82 %).

Woodlands show the lowest WFC at 0–5 cm at S3, S5 and S7, are comparable with others at four research sites, and at S4 the WFC is higher than the edible forest. It drops at 10–15 cm, mostly moderately, and at 25–30 cm either drops a little or stays the same; at S2 and S6, WFC at 25–30 cm is higher than at 10–15 cm.

As with IR, WFC alone cannot serve as an indicator of EC, though its tendencies offer limited insight into differences among the sampled ecosystems.

Figure 34. Water field capacity at all research sites and in all research places at 0-5 cm soil depth. Values adjusted to soil texture (1). All measurements done once.

Figure 35. Water field capacity at all research sites and in all research places at 15-20 cm soil depth. Values adjusted to soil texture (1). All measurements done once.

Figure 36. Water field capacity at all research sites and in all research places at 25-30 cm soil depth. Values adjusted to soil texture (1). All measurements done once.

Figure 37. Water field capacity by sampling place. All sites, soil depth 0-5 cm. All values adjusted to soil texture (1).

Figure 38. Water field capacity by sampling place. All sites, soil depth 10-15 cm. All values adjusted to soil texture (1).

Figure 39. Water field capacity by sampling place. All sites, soil depth 25-30 cm. All values adjusted to soil texture (1).

Statistical analysis

WFC (WFC_adjusted) was moderately explained by land use (conditional $R^2 = 0.61$; marginal $R^2 = 0.23$), with woodland showing significantly lower capacity than beds ($\beta = -17.83$, $p = 0.006$), and no significant effects for field or edible forest, nor for depth interactions (Figures 39 and 40).

Figure 40. Distribution of water field capacity values across study sites. X-axis shows WFC in %.

Figure 41. Distribution analysis of water field capacity in three soil depths across sampling places. X-axis shows % of WFC.

Soil organic carbon

Values of SOC were not adjusted according to texture, since the correlation between soil texture and organic carbon is not straightforward.

Descriptive analysis

SOC was the highest in woodland at S1, S3, S5, S6 and S8. S3 and S5, where woodland had a coarser texture than other sampling places, woodland still exhibits the highest SOC within site (Figure 40), suggesting that also aggregate stability plays a role

for carbon storage. In other three cases, edible forest (S2) or the bed had higher values (S4, S7) of SOC than woodland.

Figure 42. Soil organic carbon at all sites and sampling places. Measured once.

Sampling place-based analysis (Figure 41) reveals that SOC in the beds showed strong variation across sampling places, ranging from 1.8% at S3 to 17,3 % at S7. Three sites (S2, S3 and S8) had lower SOC values below 3,5%, while the others were higher. S4 (7,1%) and S5 (10,6%) stood out as intermediate–high values, and S7 reached exceptionally high SOC. Overall, most samples clustered between 2–4%, but the wide spread indicates substantial heterogeneity in SOC within the bed system, spanning from very low to extremely high concentrations.

In the edible forests, SOC values were more moderate compared with the beds, ranging from about 2% SOC (S3) up to ≈7% SOC (S6). Most samples fell in the 3–5% range, with S5 (≈5,5%) and S6 (≈7%) at the higher end. Overall, variation was less extreme than in the beds, with no single sample dominating, suggesting more consistency across the edible forest plots.

Fields had the lowest SOC percentages across all sites, ranging from 0,9% at S3 to 3% at S5. Most samples clustered at the very low end (below 2%), with only S5 reaching slightly higher values.

On permaculture beds SOC content ($\sim 6.0 \pm 0.5 \text{ g } 100 \text{ g}^{-1}$) was about 200% higher compared to fields ($\sim 2.0 \pm 0.4 \text{ g } 100 \text{ g}^{-1}$). Similarly, edible forest sites ($\sim 4.0 \pm 0.4 \text{ g } 100 \text{ g}^{-1}$) contained roughly 100% more SOC than the fields.

When looking at the sampling places across sites, we see the highest values at S7 (bed) and at S1 and S5 (woodland). Here, the SOC exceeds 14% in all cases, suggesting potential outlier status. At S7, however, the soils at other sampling places differ in texture from the bed and the differences between the bed and the edible forest and the field would likely be smaller if adjusted to a common base, indicating that the area is generally richer in SOC. Similarly, woodland values at S3, S4, S5 and S8 would likely be higher if texture correction was applied because their texture is (1), meaning that woodland outliers would be less pronounced (except for S5).

Figure 43. Soil organic carbon across research sites at all sampling places. Measured once.

Statistical analysis

SOC (SOC; log₁p-transformed) was strongly affected by land use (conditional R² = 0.65; marginal R² = 0.40), with field sites showing a significant negative effect compared to beds ($\beta = -0.75$, $p < 0.001$) and no significant effects for edible forest or woodland (Figure 44).

Figure 44. Soil organic carbon across sites. Distribution analysis.

Figure 45. Soil organic carbon. Distribution analysis.

Aggregate water stability

Descriptive analysis

Most stable aggregates were found in woodland, particularly in the upper two soil layers (observed in six cases). At site S3, however, the 10–15 cm layer in woodland was slightly less stable than in the bed and edible forest. At S4, woodland stability in the 10–15 cm layer was markedly lower than in the bed and slightly lower than in the edible forest. At S5, woodland also lagged behind the bed at this depth. A different pattern emerged at S6 and S7, where woodland was generally less stable than the bed (with the exception of the 10–15 cm layer at S6) and less stable than the edible forest. S8 presented a mixed picture, with the bed and edible forest showing similar values, though distributed differently across soil depths. Fields showed little variation between depths and consistently

exhibited the lowest aggregate stability values across sites, except at S2 (where they aligned with the bed) and S7 (where they aligned with the woodland). Figure 46 presents all sampling places at 0–5 cm soil depth, Figure 47 the 10–15 cm depth, and Figure 48 the 25–30 cm depth across sites.

Figure 46. Aggregate water stability at 0-5 cm soil depth across study sites S1-S8, sorted by sampling places. Note: Samples at S4 – Woodland consisted only of stones; therefore, the value is reported as “zero”.

Figure 47. Aggregate water stability at 10-15 cm soil depth across study sites S1-S8, sorted by sampling places.

Figure 48. Aggregate water stability at 25-30 cm soil depth across study sites S1-S8, sorted by sampling places.

Statistical analysis

AWS varied considerably across sites (Figure 49). The linear mixed model (LMM) for log-transformed AWS explained a moderate amount of variance (conditional $R^2 = 0.40$; marginal $R^2 = 0.34$). Compared with the bed, the field had a significantly lower AWS ($\beta = -1.89$, $p = 0.003$). Neither woodland ($p = 0.057$) nor edible forest ($p = 0.799$) differed significantly from the bed overall. However, a significant interaction was found for woodland at depth: the combination of woodland and the deepest soil layer (25–30 cm) showed a marked reduction in AWS relative to the bed surface ($\beta = -2.25$, $p = 0.011$). Depth alone did not have a significant main effect (Figure 50).

Figure 49. Distribution in aggregate water stability across sites.

Figure 50. Aggregate water stability across sampling places and soil depths.

Soil cover

The smallest proportion of uncovered soil was found in woodlands (Figure 51): it was zero in seven cases and 34% in one case. Edible forests across sites also exhibited a very low percentages of bare soil, mostly zero, with 5 % in one case and around 20 % in two cases. Beds varied – in two cases bare soil was close to zero, in two others it was under 10%, and in the remaining four cases it ranged between 25% and 43 %. Fields exhibited the highest proportion of bare soil in five cases, ranging from 70 to 98%. In three remaining cases, bare soil was 20 to 30% of the surface.

Figure 51. Percentage of bare soil across sites.

Statistical analysis

The model for bare soil explained a large proportion of variance, both for the fixed effects alone (marginal $R^2 = 0.61$) and for the full model including site (conditional $R^2 = 0.73$). Compared with the bed (0–5 cm), the field showed a strong positive effect, with much greater bare soil cover ($\beta = 45.38$, $p < 0.001$). In contrast, both the edible forest ($\beta = -12.38$, $p = 0.009$) and woodland ($\beta = -13.75$, $p = 0.004$) had significant negative effects relative to the bed, indicating substantially lower bare soil cover in these land uses (Figure 52).

Figure 52. Bare soil in % across sampling places.

Figure 53. Bare soil in % across study sites.

In general, site identity explained substantial variation for Infiltration and SOC, with notable contrasts among sites (e.g. S3 showing significantly lower infiltration and SOC, S5 significantly higher), and also contributed to WFC variation, though effects were weaker for Bare Soil and AWS. These results demonstrate that land use exerts a consistent and significant influence on soil structure and function, with Field systems generally associated with higher bare soil and lower soil quality indicators, Beds supporting greater infiltration and water-holding capacity, and Woodland and Edible Forest showing intermediate patterns modulated by site-specific conditions.

3.2.2.2. Soil variables related to soil fertility

Soil nutrient content

The most important soil characteristic related to fertility is **soil reaction (pH)**, which determines the availability of nutrients for plants. The optimum pH range of about 6.0–7.0 is suitable for most crops grown in fields, gardens, and orchards, although some species, such as potatoes and certain berries, have more specific requirements. Results of pH testing are presented in Figure 54. All beds reached the pH 6.0 threshold, although S6 only just met it. Edible forests were below this threshold except at S3 and S7. Fields showed a mixed picture, with S2 and S3 at or above the threshold while the others fall below it. Woodlands are moderately to strongly acidic and do not reach the threshold.

Figure 54. Soil reaction (pH) across sites and sampling places. The red line indicates the threshold of pH 6. Measured once.

Calcium (Ca) concentrations in the studied sampling places across sites are presented in Figure 55. Beds generally exhibit high levels above 3,0 g/kg, with three sites showing values between 1,5 and 2,0 g/kg. Edible forests follow a similar trend, except at S4 where Ca is lower compared to the bed. Low Ca levels in edible forests are below 1,4 g/kg in four cases. In relation to fields, Ca is lower than in the bed at seven sites, but at S3 the field has a higher level by 0,6 g/kg. Fields contain more Ca than edible forests at four sites. Woodland usually shows lower Ca levels, except at S2 where values are comparable with the bed and edible forest but higher than the field, and at S4 where they exceed the edible forest. At S5, woodland Ca exceeds 2,0 g/kg, reflecting the generally higher Ca levels at this site.

Figure 55. Calcium in surface soils (0-5 cm) across all research sites and sampling places. Measured once.

For the evaluation of other macronutrients below, the thresholds are taken from the Criteria for Evaluating the Results of Chemical Analyses of Agricultural Soils (Czech Republic, Ministry of Agriculture 1998)⁵

Results for available **magnesium (Mg)** in the studied soils show that beds generally have the highest values across sites, except at S2, where the edible forest is higher (Figure 56). According to the criteria for arable land, four beds fall into the 'very high' category, two into 'high', and two into 'good'. For fields assessed by the same criteria, two sites are 'high', one 'good', one 'sufficient', and three 'low'. Evaluation of edible forests using the criteria for grassland indicates 'low' Mg levels at S1, while the remaining sites are either 'high' or 'very high'. If criteria for orchards were used, two sites would be 'low' in Mg, three would be 'sufficient', and always one for the 'good', 'high' and 'very high' category. If orchard criteria were applied, two sites would be 'low', three 'sufficient', and one each would fall into the 'good', 'high', and 'very high' categories. Woodland generally shows very low Mg levels in four cases, slightly higher levels in three, and at S2 the concentration is comparable to the bed and edible forest, reaching a relatively high value of about 600 mg/kg.

⁵ <https://www.zakonyprolidi.cz/cs/1998-275>

Figure 56. Magnesium in surface soils (0-5 cm) across all research sites and sampling places. Measured once.

Plant available **potassium (K)** at sampling places across sites is presented in Figure 57. Across the sites, beds generally exhibited the highest K values, with the exception of S2 and S3, where edible forests were higher. Interpretation of these results requires consideration of soil texture, which influences K availability. Based on standard arable land thresholds, K levels in the beds were classified as ‘very high’ in five cases, ‘high’ in one case and ‘good’ in two cases. Fields, in contrast, showed greater variability, ranging from ‘very high’ in two cases, to ‘sufficient’ in two cases, and ‘low’ in three cases. Edible forests, when interpreted against grassland reference values, reached ‘very high’ levels in two cases, ‘high’ in two, ‘good’ in one, and ‘sufficient’ in two cases. If the thresholds for orchards were used, S6 would fall to ‘low’ and three cases would be ‘sufficient’, two ‘good’, one ‘high’ and only one ‘very high’. Woodlands consistently had the lowest values, although S2 and S8 were exceptions, where K levels exceeded those in the corresponding fields.

Figure 57. Potassium in surface soils (0-5 cm) across all research sites and sampling places

The amount of plant-available **phosphorus (P)** in soils at the sampling places is shown in Figure 58. Beds contained the highest P concentrations across sites, ranging from 218 to 1302 mg/kg, with some sites (S4, S5) exceeding other sampling places by an order of magnitude. Edible forests and fields showed considerable variation, ranging from 96 to 373 mg/kg and from 86 to 338 mg/kg respectively. These P values are classified as 'high' to 'very high' for grassland and 'satisfactory' to 'very high' for orchards and 'good' to 'very high' for arable land. They do not indicate a shortage of available P: thresholds for insufficient P measured by SP are set at below 50 mg/kg for fields and below 55 mg/kg for special crops such as orchards. Woodlands generally had the lowest P values, ranging from 55 to 338 mg/kg, with S2 and S5 having the highest values. The influence of site conditions is evident: S5 showed high P values across all sampling places, while S6 consistently exhibited lower concentrations.

Figure 58. Phosphorus in surface soils (0-5 cm) across all research sites and sampling places

3.2.2.3. Ecosystem variables related to microclimate regulation

Air temperature

Here, I first present the successful recordings and then recordings that require conditional interpretation. As noted in Chapter 2.2.5.2, some measurements could not be used, because of technical failures. Consequently, in some cases, comparisons were possible only between two sampling places (S2) or could not include the field sampling place (S1, S7, S8). To examine how sampling places responded to extreme temperatures, I selected:

- the hottest-day week of the measured period
- the coldest-day week of the measured period

Following the descriptive analysis of each study site, a summary of findings is provided.

At S2, data are available for the bed and field. The datalogger in the woodland failed. During the period with the hottest days of the week, both bed and field showed daytime maxima generally ranging from 20 to over 30 °C and night-time minima from around 9 to 15 °C (Figure 59). The field reached slightly higher daytime peaks, up to about 32 °C, while the bed was 1–2 °C lower at maximum, once about 0,6 °C higher. At night the field cooled often 2–3 °C below the bed on the hot days. As a result, daily swings were larger in the field, reaching 22,8 °C, compared with 18,6 °C on the day of the largest swing in the bed.

Figure 59. Hottest-day week at S2, data logged at 3-hours interval.

In the week with the coldest day at S2, night-time temperatures in both bed and field frequently dropped below $-5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, with the bed often $1\text{--}2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ colder at minima. In contrast, daytime peaks were higher in the field, occasionally reaching $4\text{--}6\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, while the bed lagged slightly behind. This meant the field experienced sharper daily swings of $8\text{--}10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, compared to more moderated fluctuations in the bed. Overall, the field warmed faster during sunny hours but cooled quickly at night, whereas the bed showed slower changes, maintaining a more buffered though generally cooler profile in winter conditions (Figure 60).

Figure 60. Coldest-day week at S2, data logged at 3-hours intervals.

At **S3**, all sampling places yielded data. In the week with the warmest day, bed and field followed a very similar pattern (Figure 61). Bed reached higher daytime maxima than the field by 0,5 °C on the hottest day and up to 3 °C on other days, while field exceeded bed once by 0,5 °C. Field sometimes peaked for longer than the bed. Their transitions between night-time lows and daytime highs were equally steep, with bed being colder at night by up to 1,7 °C. Woodland, by contrast, reached lower daytime maxima of 28,9 °C at the highest, 6,6 °C cooler than bed, and maintained higher night-time minima of 4,9 °C, 4,8 °C warmer than the bed. Its transitions were more gradual, with flattened daytime peaks and slower evening declines.

Figure 61. Hottest-day week at S3, data logged at 1-hour interval.

In the week with the coldest day, bed and field follow a similar pattern even more, showing night-time minima of 7,4 and 5 °C respectively and daytime maxima of 14,1 and 13,4 °C respectively, with field typically slightly colder. Both sustained their daytime peaks around the same time. Woodland diverged more strongly at night, remaining up to 4 °C warmer than bed. During the day the difference between woodland and the open sites narrowed, with woodland maxima only 2–4 °C lower than bed and field. Transitions in woodland were smoother, while bed and field showed steeper shifts between highs and lows (Figure 62).

Figure 62. Coldest-day week at S3, data logged at 1-hour intervals.

At **S4**, all sampling places yielded data (Figure 63) at least for 2 months. Here, the week with the hottest day shows that field reached the highest peaks, up to 44,6 °C, while bed followed slightly lower at 38,9 °C and woodland remained cooler at 35,5 °C. At hot days field was up to 7,5 °C warmer than bed and around 9 °C warmer than woodland in general. Night-time minima were more similar across sampling places, with woodland occasionally 6 °C warmer than the others and bed slightly warmer than field. Field sustained its highest day values for longer, forming broad plateaus at peak heat, while bed's plateaus were less hot and declined sooner. Woodland showed the most gradual transitions with flatter peaks and smoother evening declines.

Figure 63. Hottest-day week at S4, data logged at 3-hours intervals.

For a week with the coldest day, selection possibilities at S4 were limited since the data logger in the field stopped recording in late August. Figure 64 therefore represents a week with the coldest day, although daytime temperatures were warm, because it was a July week. Bed and field followed similar curves, with bed generally warmer at night and showing shorter daytime peaks that were up to 2 °C lower than in the field, though on two days bed briefly exceeded field by up to 3 °C. These peaks in bed were shorter by several hours. Relating to lower temperatures in the beginning of the week, the bed is more similar to the woodland that had day temperature lower than the field by 8 °C and night temperatures by 1,6 °C. At the start of the week, when temperatures were lower, bed resembled woodland more closely, with daytime values around 8 °C lower than field and night-time values 1,6 °C lower. Woodland displayed a cooler, flatter daytime curve and a warmer, less extreme night-time curve. In the coldest night, woodland was 5 °C warmer than field and 2,5 % warmer than bed.

Figure 64. Coldest-day week at S4, data logged at 3-hours intervals.

At **S5**, all sampling places were successfully recorded. The hottest-day week in October (Figure 65) shows that bed daytime maxima of around 22–25 °C were consistently 7–10 °C lower than field maxima and only 2–3 °C higher than woodland. At night, bed cooled to about 3 °C, closely matching field, while woodland remained up to 3 °C warmer, marking the clearest night-time difference. The shape of the curve in bed showed sharp daily rises and shorter peaks, resembling woodland more closely than field. Both bed and woodland displayed quicker transitions to lower temperatures by about 3 hours, with woodland maintaining slightly higher values at night and for longer time.

Figure 66. Coldest-day week at S5, data logged at 3-hours intervals.

At **S7**, measurements were successful. Here, we have comparison of bed, edible forest and woodland. During the hottest-day week, bed showed the highest temperatures, exceeding those of edible forest by 3–7 °C and those of woodland by 6–12 °C (40,1 °C vs. 37 °C vs. 31 °C on the hottest day). At night, bed and edible forest were similar, with edible forest being slightly higher by about 1,5 °C, while woodland remained up to 5 °C warmer than bed. Curves of bed were sharper and the peaks lasted longer than in the edible forest. Both of these sampling places contrasted with woodland, which displayed flatter curves and slower transitions. Overall, the edible forest lay in between the extremes of bed and woodland (Figure 67).

Figure 67. Hottest-day week at S7, data logged at 1-hour interval

During the coldest-day week at S7, bed showed the largest day–night differences, ranging from $-5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ at night to $16\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ during the day, while both edible forest and woodland stayed within a narrower range of $-5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $6\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. In general, bed displayed the most pronounced peaks and minima. Edible forest followed bed in its night-time minima but matched woodland in its daytime highs. Woodland maintained the highest night-time temperatures, with flatter curves and smoother transitions compared to the sharper fluctuations of bed and edible forest (Figure 68).

Figure 68. Coldest-day week at S7, data logged at 1-hour interval

Data collection at **S8** in 2021 that followed failed data recording in 2018 has yielded records for bed, edible forest and woodland. The hottest-day week revealed large differences between woodland and the permaculture sampling places. On the hottest day, woodland reached only 25,6 °C, compared to 39,6 °C in the edible forest and 38,8 °C in the bed. The edible forest often exceeded the bed by up to 9 °C, and, like the bed, showed large daily swings of up to 38 °C. Woodland, on the contrary exhibited the maximum day-night range of 12 °C, mostly lower. The transition curves of bed and edible forest were closely aligned, while woodland showed much smoother fluctuation (Figure 69).

Figure 69. Hottest-day week at S8, data logged at 1-hour interval.

During the coldest-day week at S8, the same pattern observed in the hottest-day week was evident on the warmer days (Figure 70) but on the cooler days the differences between the three sampling places were reduced. At night, bed and edible forest reached similar minima, with only about 1,5 °C separating them from woodland. During the day, however, woodland remained cooler, with maxima up to 9 °C lower than bed on the coolest days. Edible forest showed lower daytime values on cool days than bed, by up to 3,8 °C.

Figure 70. Coldest-day week at S8, data logged at 1-hour interval.

Data collected at both S1 and S6 share one feature: the woodland data logger was hidden for safety reasons. This placement affected the results, as the cover up retained moisture for long periods and distorted the measurements. This limitation must be taken into account when interpreting the woodland data. Nevertheless, the records still provide valuable insight into the microclimate dynamics of bed and edible forest.

At **S1**, the transition curves of bed and edible forest were very similar on the hottest days, with bed reaching higher daytime maxima of 45 °C vs 39,4°C in edible forest. Night temperatures were lower in the bed than in the edible forest, resulting in larger day-night swings of up to 34 °C compared to (27 °C) edible forest on the hottest days. Temperatures rose earlier in the day in edible forest but also dropped several hours earlier. Woodland, which has to be considered with caution here, showed more stable temperatures with very gradual rises and falls (Figure 71).

Figure 71. Hottest-day week at S1, data logged at 1-hour interval. Woodland data logger hidden in a hollow tree stump.

During the coldest-day week at S1, there were no large differences between bed and edible forest, either in the peaks, the lows or the transition curves. On the coldest days, as in the previous week presented, edible forest's temperature rose earlier in the day but also declined sooner. Woodland, which must be interpreted with caution, showed much lower values and a flatter transition curve (Figure 72).

Figure 72. Coldest-day week at S1, data logged at 1-hour interval. Woodland data logger hidden in a hollow tree stump.

At **S6**, there was the same situation for data collection (data logger hidden under wood in the woodland, although less isolated from climate than at S1) and data were also collected for three sampling places.

The hottest-day week (Figure 73) shows the same patterns as S1, with the only difference that lowest night temperatures in the bed were the same, not lower, as in the edible forest. Woodland, that only can be considered with caution, also shows very similar patterns to woodland at S1.

Figure 73. Hottest-day week at S6, data logged at 1-hour interval. Woodland data logger placed on a tree stem and covered by a thick piece of bark.

The coldest-day week at S6 (Figure 74) shows also the same patterns as S1, with the edible forest reaching colder dips at night (by 6 °C) but reaching less high during the day (up to 6 °C) than the bed. The woodland, which has to be considered with caution shows flat curves and low temperature swings of maximum 12 °C.

Figure 74. Coldest-day week at S6, data logged at 1-hour interval. Woodland data logger placed on a tree stem and covered by a thick piece of bark.

Descriptive summary of findings – microclimate regulation

The data show a varied picture. Permaculture beds generally followed the temperature dynamics of the field rather than the woodland. From the group of eight observed periods on four farms, they demonstrated better microclimate stabilization in five cases, but were similar to the field in three cases. On hot days, beds were typically a few degrees cooler than the field, although at some sites they reached similar values or even slightly higher maxima. Their daytime peaks were sometimes shorter and declined sooner, with smoother transitions than those of the field. At night, bed temperatures were either lower, similar to or slightly higher than those of the field across sites, usually within a range of a few degrees. On moderately cold days, beds tended to follow the woodland pattern, but with higher night-time temperatures than woodland. An exception was observed at S3, where the bed exhibited larger day–night fluctuations than both the woodland and the field, differing by a few degrees.

The edible forest showed a relationship to the bed similar to that of the bed to the field. In five out of the eight timeframes observed at four research sites, it exhibited better

microclimate stabilization properties than the bed; in two cases, it was very similar to the bed, and in one case, it was worse than the bed. Its curves were often of comparable duration, with daytime peaks sometimes higher and sometimes lower than those of the bed, both on hot or cold days. When edible forest peaks were lower and more similar to woodland during the day (typically on colder days), its night-time temperatures aligned more closely with the bed than with woodland. No comparison is available between field and edible forest, which would have been useful on sites where edible forest exhibited higher peaks than the bed.

Woodland, by contrast, displayed a consistent pattern across sites: its curves were the flattest, the temperature ranges the narrowest, and the transitions the most gradual.

3.2.2.4. Ecosystem variable related to pest control

Predation rate

Predation rate was measured on six Czech research sites. The areas of beds and edible forest were combined and treated as 'permaculture', with fields serving as the control. Table 75 presents the results that showed a varied picture, with a predominantly better results for permaculture. Predation rate was higher by 13% the lowest at S8 and up to 6-fold at S4. Within two permaculture sites, the wilder areas of beds or edible forest had better results, which was noted during the collection of bite sticks. The same was observed at the field at S6 with a near field edges and vegetation. Here, predation rate was 50%. Interesting is the result at S8 with no huge difference between permaculture and field. The field had poppy plants and *Aphis fabae* was predated very strongly on this site, resulting in over 60% predation rate.

Figure 75. Predation rate on six Czech research sites.

3.2.2.5. Ecosystem variable related to erosion control

Wind erosion

Wind erosion sampling was not successful. Regardless of location, the bottles were almost empty, sometimes containing dead insect and no soil. Measured weight was tiny (Table 12).

Table 12. Results of wind erosion measurement (data not usable). N/A=results unavailable due to circumstances, – = erosion sampler not placed.

Research site	Bed	Edible forest	Field	Forest
S1	0,1 g	–	N/A	N/A
S2	<0,1 g	–	0,2 g	<0,1 g
S3	<0,1 g	–	–	-
S4	0,1 g	–	N/A	<0,1 g
S5	0,1 g	–	<0,1 g	N/A
S6	<0,1 g	0,2 g	–	–
S7	<0,1 g	<0,1 g		
S8	0,1 g	–	0,3	<0,1 g

Several factors influenced the failed outcome of the sampling method:

- The erosion sampler should have been placed lower from the beginning of the study, 50 cm was too high (Sterk & Raats, 1996).
- The bottles should probably have been placed horizontally (Sterk & Raats, 1996)
- It would have been necessary to have many more samplers across a larger area, such as 30 pieces/ha (Webb et al., 2016).

As a result, I obtained only indicative observations rather than usable data, and this measurement was excluded as a variable of an ecosystem service.

3.2.3. Regulating services provided by permaculture ecosystems

According to above-described results, Table 13 presents the overall delivery trends of regulating ecosystem services in permaculture, in relation to both positive and negative references. Outliers are addressed in the discussion.

Table 13. Regulating ES provided by permaculture. Arrows show whether the service is higher, lower or the same as provided by the reference unit. N/A indicates no data.

Ecosystem service / Natures' contribution to people	Permaculture vs. field vs. woodland
Habitat creation and maintenance	↑ / N/A
Biodiversity	↑ / ↑
Microclimate regulation	↑ / ↓
Pest control / Regulation of detrimental organisms	↑ / N/A
Flood control / Regulation of hazards and extreme events	↑ / ↑
Erosion control / Protection of soils	↑ / →
Soil fertility / Formation of soils	↑ / ↑

3.3. Biodiversity

Because biodiversity underpins multiple types of ES, I present biodiversity findings separately here.

Plant species diversity

Plant species richness (S) counts showed that edible forests had the highest number of species per 0.41 m² in six of the eight study sites, while beds were highest at two sites (Figure 76). Across sites, woodland generally contained fewer species, averaging 37% lower than beds and 48% lower than edible forests. At individual sites, woodland values ranged from being slightly higher than beds (S2, S4) to more than 70% lower (S3, S7). Fields had the lowest number at all sites, ranging between one and 3,7 species per sampling plot (Figure 77).

Figure 76. Plant species diversity at all study sites and their respective sampling places.

Figure 77. Plant species diversity at all study sites (S1-S8) grouped by types of sampling places.

Habitat diversity

Habitats present at the permaculture sites were recorded; however, no comparison with fields or woodlands was undertaken in this case. The aim was to capture the range of habitat types observed within the approximate one to two-hectare area where sampling took place. Figure 78 presents these findings, which are intended as an overview rather than an exhaustive inventory.

Figure 78. Habitats identified at permaculture sites.

Sixteen distinct landscape structures were identified, of which six were primarily used for food or herb production. The most common were mixed vegetable beds, combining permanent and annual crops, which were present at all sites. Mixed flower beds with a similar combination were also found. Raised beds, monoculture beds, and greenhouses were present at some sites. Heaps with vegetation represented a particular structure resulting from terrain adjustments; rather than removing soil, these mounds were maintained and planted with perennials. In some cases, such as at site S6, they were created from accumulated plant material and later planted (Figure 79).

Figure 79. Heaps with vegetation before planting and after at S6.

Other structural elements supporting biodiversity included seminatural vegetation patches and shrub thickets. These would usually surround the edible forest consisting of three layers: herbaceous, shrub and trees layer. The edible forest typically comprised three layers: herbaceous, shrub, and tree strata. In some sites, animal husbandry was present, with chicken fields and/or pastures. Fruit orchards also occurred, differing from edible forests in that they consisted only of trees with grassland beneath, without an emphasis on multiple layers. Meadows were also present at several sites, mown both for biodiversity purposes and for hay provision when required. Water bodies were represented either by natural swimming pools or smaller pools serving both animals and plants. Wood piles were found at all sites, either intentionally established as deadwood habitats (Figure 80) or as temporary storage for later use.

Figure 80. Wood pile as habitat at S8.

3.4. Non-material benefits

My findings show that permaculture ecosystems provide the following non-material benefits to their inhabitants, users, creators, and visitors. The frequency of how often they were mentioned—either directly or indirectly—through the narratives shared by respondents is shown in Figure 81.

Figure 81. Frequency of occurrences of pre-defined non-material benefit categories, based on deductive coding of interview data. Categories are ordered from most to least frequently mentioned across all participants.

Here I present the findings according to the non-material benefits categories. The themes within the categories are described according to their occurrence

3.4.1. Learning and knowledge

Learning and knowledge emerged as the most frequently mentioned benefit, with over 240 references across interviews. All participants acknowledged it, with educators mentioning it up to four times more than others.

The dominant theme was **experiential learning** about gardening and ecological principles. Several participants described permaculture as a guiding framework that allowed them to engage with longstanding interests. One participant reflected: *'I loved digging in the soil as a child... Permaculture fitted into the mosaic because it opened up a completely different dimension of food growing.'* Participants also valued learning how to grow their own food or cultivate poor soils. A key subtheme was the development of **systems thinking**, that is part of the PDC training. Participants viewed their sites as integrated systems. A participant, who started the project on a former grassland, explained: *'I see that the ecosystem gets healthier as it becomes more complicated and stable.'* Practices such as composting, seed-saving, mulching, and integrating animals reflect this understanding of ecological interdependence. This mindset extends to **biodiversity-friendly attitudes**, such as welcoming weeds for pollinators or appreciating fallen leaves and windbreaks for their ecological functions. Harmonious interactions—like planning sowing based on phenology—demonstrate how detailed observation informs decision-making. **Hands-on engagement and observation** were recurring topics, crucial for gaining insights. One participant noted: *'In permaculture, we're always observing... what and why is happening?'* Observation leads to practical applications—such as site redesign or pest management—and sometimes to non-intervention, as when one participant watched a tree respond to rabbit damage: *'I see that the tree has the ability to self-renew.'* Participants also engage in more **open-ended observation** of wildlife and seasonal processes. One participant remarked: *'I didn't consciously know how an acorn grows... This can be surprisingly life-changing.'* Another shared joy in observing solitary bee species. The site itself was also once described as 'an observation project.' Some participants described learning **broader life principles** from nature, including abundance, generosity, and the necessity to be connected with nature as humans as it fosters peace, harmony and inner connection, making us 'more human'. Nature teaches about natural harmony embedded in the web of various beings, functions and processes, such as trees converting sunlight into biomass and cooling the environment. **Children** benefit too. Eight participants highlighted that permaculture sites help children understand where food comes from, experience the seasons, and develop life skills through hands-on exploration. Parents described this as a kind of 'natural school'. For educators, the sites serve as **testing grounds and teaching tools**. They

offer courses, tours, and blogs that reach thousands. Participant whose activities on site educate hundreds of people per year, emphasized: *'The whole meaning of the project is to get people gardening.'* These sites act as **ambassadors**, inspiring others to engage with ecological food production. Similarly, some Czech sites that only do informal tours of the place were founded with the idea to inspire others in the background.

3.4.2. Activity benefit

Activity was the second most frequently mentioned benefit, with 165 references across interviews. All participants discussed it between 21 and seven times, particularly through gardening, caretaking, and recreational practices. I identified four themes. The most commonly described theme was **growing food and 'gardening'**, which involves establishing permaculture spaces and engaging in various types of physical labour. One participant shared: *'Working with the soil, which I have always felt drawn to.'* Participants value the site for providing space for this fulfilling activity, with planting and sowing being particularly popular. Successful plant growth requires experience and often involves trial and error influenced by site conditions and climate. **Experimentation** featured strongly in these descriptions, with 25% mentions overlapping with learning. Participants tried mushroom cultivation, seed propagation, grafting, growing exotic plants, mulching to conserve water and protect soil, and producing heat from compost. Others crossed plant varieties or chicken breeds. One interviewee described how their site began on bare grassland, requiring improvisation with materials and techniques like 'Hugelkultur'⁶. The site design often changed during implementation, with creativity and adaptation shaping the process. **Harvesting** was often discussed alongside gardening. One participant called it *'shopping in the garden'*, adding: *'From spring to autumn, I enjoy picking something and cooking a meal from it.'* Picking apples, pears, and berries was often enjoyed as a family activity, in stark contrast to store-bought produce. **Caretaking** tasks included mulching, pruning, composting, maintaining plant health and tending to animals like ducks, chickens, and sheep. One participant with previous experience as an organic farmer, described caring for a meadow to ensure diverse plant species that provide high quality fodder for livestock. Active observation is integral to these activities, allowing participants to check on seed

⁶ A mound bed constructed from decaying wood and other compostable plant material.

germination or harvest readiness. Daily walks to cover the garden area were reported, especially by male participants *'I walk randomly, trying to cover the whole garden somehow. If I don't manage it in one day, I take a different route the next day.'* At the Belgian cooperative farm, a group meets to 'communicate with plants' to ensure their well-being—a practice that the participant described as somewhat irrational. **Building the site** as *'a functioning ecosystem'* was another major theme. Participants described designing the whole site first and then establishing hedgerows, woodlands, edible forests, coppicing forests, a mother apple orchard with many different varieties, vegetable and perennial beds, wild areas, meadows, water bodies or dry-stone walls. Planting trees and shrubs, often grown from seed or propagated by grafting, is highlighted as a significant activity. One participant reflected: *'Planting a tree feels beautiful.'* Those eager to grow food immediately had to innovate, using local materials in place of unfinished compost and employing Hugelkultur to create beds and soil. The process was often described as open-ended, with creative changes happening over time. Although the projects have been ongoing for years, interviewees view them as never truly finished and welcome the opportunity for creativity. Adjustments made over time focus on details rather than altering the overarching permaculture design. These activities were often described as fulfilling rather than burdensome. As one participant remarked: *'All homestead activities are beautiful.'* The range of daily tasks offered variety and a sense of freedom. Another one shared: *'In the beginning I did all the hard work...now I'm slowly learning all these things too.'* Visitors were also keen to join in. At one farm, some 'picked up the rake' as soon as they arrived. Despite the physical demands, these activities were often described as having a relaxing effect.

Other physical activities, including relaxing and meditative practises were the second most common theme. **Walking** the site (also with children) allowed participants to observe seasonal changes and find quiet spots to relax. Some compared the experience to walking a labyrinth, after paths were mowed, which they found intriguing. After mowing with a scythe, one participant remembers enjoyable cooling off in a natural lake with her son. Others described lying in a grove, meditating, or simply watching the sky. Sitting on a bench or rock became a way to pause and observe. Visitors to the sites reported too that this natural setting facilitates a quicker entry into a relaxed state. The **theme of play**

was mentioned multiple times; one participant enjoys creatively playing with a water stream, while another plays the didgeridoo in the middle of the edible orchard. An employee said: *'It often reminds me of my childhood when I played outside; I feel like a kid again in the garden. It sometimes feels like a game.'* **Social gatherings** were an important part of site life. Seven participants across five sites mentioned music sessions, dance nights, film screenings, solstice celebrations, and weddings. These were attended by the local community, friends or family members. Informal conversations also occurred during tours or while chatting with staff, guests, or volunteers at the Belgian professional sites.

3.4.3. Identity

The **identity benefit** was mentioned by all participants, with 101 total references. Mentions ranged from 4 to 19, the lowest from the employee and the highest from a female respondent who has lived on-site for 17 years. The rest were fairly evenly distributed. A key theme was **social identity**, experienced as belonging to a community of like-minded people who live nearby or friends who come to visit. At professional sites, participants valued being part of the team. Those rooted in the community highlighted its importance: *'And I'm glad we're here, because here there's that contact, the roots are here, and there are friends, and the community works much better here...'* Another theme was **embodied personal identity**, where participants consider themselves as someone whose identity is closely tied to working and being in the permaculture site in close connection with nature. For some of them it was the role of a gardener or farmer. Others had difficulties with a definition, because they just 'did what they enjoyed' and expressed it another way: *'There is a part of me in the garden,'* and *'I feel more whole in the garden.'* Daily or seasonal rituals were described, often related to the care of the land. I also found a theme of **value-based identity** tied to permaculture as a worldview. Being a 'permaculturist' or 'ecologist' helped participants align their lives with core values and natural tendencies. *'When you realise your own responsibility, you can take your power back...'* said one. The employee added: *'I never felt as happy at work as now... it goes deep, finally in my life.'* These values—respect, diversity, altruism—were often rooted in childhood: being drawn to nature, enjoying soil, animals, forests, and outdoor play. One reflected: *'I went into a rabbit house and locked myself inside, because I wanted to know what life was like from their*

perspective.’ Others spoke of the permaculture practice as central to living a good life: *‘We are more human when we are connected to nature.’*

3.4.4. Aesthetics

Aesthetics was mentioned 102 times across all participants, ranging from six to 17 mentions per person. All participants assign high **aesthetic value** to permaculture ecosystems, but emphasise that the notion of beauty is different, because it arises from naturalness and semi-wilderness. The site is both a functional space—a healthy ecosystem that also produces food—and a space where beauty can thrive. As one participant put it: *‘I wanted functionality and yield, but also harmony—elements that might not be profitable but create beauty, like flowers that bloom while repelling pests.’* Therefore, rather than being highly organised and neat, permaculture beauty is often found in the richness of organic forms, plant species (often in the form of polycultures), layers, colours, and plant ages, an aesthetics illustrated in Figure 82. This aesthetic appreciation is often linked to the knowledge that the biodiversity of species and their habitats should be supported: *‘Some trees may not be for people, but are good for birds. That’s what I like about permaculture—it recognises those different purposes.’* This may find expression in the belief that **what is natural is also perfect and therefore beautiful**. As one explained: *‘Beauty for me depends on many things...for example, you see a dandelion and you know it’s good for bees after the winter. Then you look in the next garden—there’s a robot, a fence, all sterile. It’s like two completely different ways of seeing nature.’* Interviewees found uncovered soil and monocultures aesthetically unpleasing; bare soil was occasionally described as ‘strange.’ Blooming of flowers was mentioned many times, sometimes as part of a living whole: *‘What I love most visually are the flowers mingling with everything and the insects flying around. The fruit trees line the edges and birds always scatter when you walk by.’* Walking through the site evokes sensory and emotional experiences: *‘Every step offers a new perspective that pleases the eye.’* Participants also recognise **their own role in shaping this beauty**—not by creating order, but by complementing nature: *‘I’m happy if I’ve helped a harmonious chaos emerge there.’* In fact, the development of the site design is often inspired by visual impressions and guided by intuition and personal judgement. Many say the site should be nice and aesthetically pleasing to others.

Figure 82. Intersection of biodiversity and habitats underpinning the different elements of permaculture aesthetics.

3.4.5. Heritage

Heritage was mentioned 89 times across interviews. There were between two and 14 mentions of it among participants. Four overlapping themes were identified. The most frequently mentioned were **happy childhood memories relating to specific individuals**, especially grandparents, and their garden or farm. It was mentioned most by the farmer on inherited land and least by the employee. A Czech interviewee recalled: *'I spent my whole childhood at my grandma's... she had sheep, goats, rabbits, and a huge garden.'* Seven participants described early gardening experiences, mostly in hobby weekend plots. One participant claimed the grandparents practiced permaculture unconsciously, because the farm had so many diverse elements and recalls visiting them as joyful and formative. These memories often re-emerged in current practices. One participant noted: *'When I call the chickens, I sometimes get a glimpse of the memory of my grandmother doing the same and I have the feeling that 'everything is all right'.* Or, they can be embodied in a sense of family continuity: *'My ancestors were here and my descendants will be here... it's such an obligation.'* Others also described continuing family

heritage, either from the grandparents or, as in case of the professional participant, from the parents where the mother is an experienced herbalist. But, as he illustrates, family legacies were not always simple: *'My grandfather had a great dislike for this project because it was not the way a farmer should work.'* Another Czech interviewee described his great-grandfather's land being expropriated during collectivization, which shapes his own reluctance to be too attached to his land. traditions—once from the maternal grandparents, and once through learning from his mother, an herbalist. Family legacies were not always simple. M7 recalled: *'My grandfather had a great dislike for this project because it was not the way a farmer should work.'* M8 described his great-grandfather's land being expropriated during collectivization, which led to emotional distance from land ownership. Interestingly, some participants voiced a pattern where their relationship with farming or gardening came through their parents, but was often linked to gardening styles or activities they disliked. Two female participants described how their mother's gardening methods put them off until they found permaculture. A subtheme relates to specific **plants and animals and working with them**, mentioned by eight participants in connection with loved ones. Examples include growing peonies, monarda, mint and marigolds. One expressed a desire to plant a pear variety linked to his grandmother, stating, *'That's what I really want, this one act, because it will always remind me of her.'* Another recalled how observing his grandparents' practises in the 1960s shaped his approach to farming today. Another noted a return to traditional methods, recalling, *'I went back to my grandmother's experience... to the realisation that you just have to do it that way.'* For seven participants, the **heritage of the place** itself was important. Those living on ancestral land emphasized deep familiarity. One explained: *'It's the only thing that makes sense... If you don't know the place well, you might be surprised by things that wouldn't surprise you otherwise.'* Others developed a strong sense of place even without family ties. One story involved recognizing the practical reasons behind old building placements: *'When the wind blew, the leaves remained still down by the house, indicating intentional design.'* The final theme concerned **traditional practices** that resonated with permaculture. M1 said: *'People have always farmed this way... small fields, orchards, wild zones. It reflects a natural coexistence with the land.'* Two others described the diverse production on old farms, highlighting the circularity of the system they are trying to establish. One female interviewee recalled

social connections formed during traditional labour such as goose plucking, which she now remembers while sewing shoes in a local women's group.

3.4.6. Spirituality

This benefit was mentioned 57 times by all but one participant, with individual mentions ranging from one to thirteen. A common theme is the sense of **wholeness**—the idea that everything in nature, including humans, is part of something bigger. Sometimes, it resonates with 'life' as such. Permaculture is described as a way of maintaining life. Some participants call it 'oneness,' with perspectives ranging from the planet being *sacred* to nature being something that transcends us. Many emphasized that physical connection to nature is essential to experiencing this whole. Permaculture sites were seen as natural spaces that help foster presence and alignment with life. Participants expressed **wonder at nature's intelligence**, describing ecosystems as effortlessly functional despite their diversity. One interviewee said: *'I'm continually amazed by nature's intelligence. From the cleverness of birds to the mimicry of plants. I find something new to marvel at in the garden almost every day.'* Animals were also seen as essential parts of the 'whole'. One participant noted: *'The pigs and chickens are connected to the whole and should have a good life.'* Similarly, another emphasized a non-discriminatory view of plant species, seeing wisdom even in non-natives.

This sense of belonging to a greater whole led many to express **respect for life and a sense of responsibility**. A female participant noted: *'A person can change something only through their own life and actions.'* Because everything is interconnected, participants felt that harm in one area affects all. Once, the permaculture site was likened to 'groves of wisdom,' that should be established by more people, as spaces where they can garden and meet their needs but also reconnect with life. This regenerative effort stems from love for the Earth. Another added: *'What drew me to permaculture was its affirmation of my connection to the earth... My actions matter and therefore, there is the responsibility.'* Another quote summarizes it: *'When I view it this way, I sense something that transcends us... We can engage with it, find inspiration, and contribute to harmony—or choose destruction.'*

Many participants described **a reverence for wilderness and certain plants or places**, which they considered sacred. Old trees serve as guardians of the land, while groves

inspired respectful, machine-free care. For example, one respondent reflects on a grove with cherry trees and a stone field: *‘There’s a sea of stones that gives it a sacred vibe. I sometimes wonder if I should really be taking a stone from there.’* Such places were also used for meditation and quiet reflection. At one site, trees planted at the birth of children were especially meaningful, seen as ‘powerful’ not only by parents but by the children themselves, who formed strong attachments to their apple, hornbeam, or chestnut trees. The Belgian cooperative site is designed around a geobiological energetic centre, with beds arranged in circles, resembling ripples in water. Interviewees from the site express scepticism but respected the idea. Described **spiritual experiences** at the site included encounters with animals such as the guardian in the form of a wolfhound or embodying a dragonfly during an animal circle ceremony. At one site, ceremonies are held to connect with the elves and spirits of plants, trees, and the Earth.

3.4.7. Bequest

This benefit was mentioned 52 times, between two and seven times by each participant. Three themes were identified. All participants acknowledged the importance of bequest concerning **children**, which accounted for over 60% of the total mentions. I identified four dimensions: 1) fostering an experience and connection with nature, nurturing a sense of wonder; 2) creating a legacy that allows children and grandchildren to care for the land and garden; 3) providing a space of refuge and inspiration for future family members; and 4) instilling values of sustainability, self-reliance, and respect for the environment. Bequest related to **the human-nature relationship** overlaps with the bequest concerning children in more than half of the cases. This aspect emphasises inspiring future generations to create healthy spaces through natural gardening; for some, this is the project's primary purpose. Another interviewee stated, *‘Here, they can feel nature’s generosity, in this world...that gives a lot of hope and optimism.’* They mentioned a desire to support a respectful, collaborative and harmonious coexistence with nature, foster confidence in managing and engaging with it, and to instil a love for nature—even in those kids uninterested in gardening. A final theme concerned **preserving seeds and animals** for future generations. This was seen as vital for genetic diversity, education, and future food security. Participants described collecting and saving seeds, particularly of native, old, and rare varieties, as part of passing on knowledge about food production and the link between

plants, soil, and human sustenance. One remarked: *'I see preserving plants and animals as an obligation... If there is only rapeseed everywhere that depletes the soil, what will we do then?'* While not always a primary motivation, many felt a duty to protect these resources for the future.

3.4.8. Sense of place

Sense of place was mentioned over 50 times, with individual mentions ranging from two to eight. The highest frequency came from participants at scenic sites, especially those with expansive views. Participants expressed **enjoyment of the whole site**, often naming multiple favourite spots. One said: *'It's a "wow" wherever you stop and look.'* Sites were described as beautiful, peaceful, and rich in character, with the site at 'Gallow Hill' noted for its *genius loci*. Horizon views were especially appreciated— *'I would miss the sunset with the hills'*—while overlooks gave a sense of a broader perspective. Respondents enjoyed these settings while resting on benches or rocks, being in a lake or taking breaks from work. Visitors allegedly also noticed the site's beauty and positive energy and liked to return. Sometimes, **favourite spots** were described vividly, such as one with a linden tree and daisies: *'I feel very safe there.'* Some vantage points served as spaces for reflection and planning. **Relationships to place** were often emotional. Participants spoke of love, safety, or not wanting to leave. Others struggled to describe their connection: *'The relationship with this place is very subtle and incommunicable... you really have to experience the garden for yourself.'* The feeling of **being 'at home'** was mentioned often, with some linking locations to life events like weddings. Even those who do not live on-site expressed deep connection, for example as a committed to contributing to the place's uniqueness. The site was also seen as a **space for creative expression**, establishing *'a beautiful piece of earth.'* A female interviewee added: *'I carry the concept of the space in me... I'd do the same elsewhere if I had to leave.'* Creativity was also connected to material benefits the site provides: *'You have the potential for creativity, like growing mushrooms.'* In one case, a lifestyle centred on food production developed only after buying the place, initially chosen for its stunning beauty. **Psychologically**, the site helped people feel open, joyful and connected with nature. It nurtured a feeling of novelty when seeing new growing things emerging. **Specific aesthetic values** were mentioned less frequently in a direct relation to the place value. Some appreciated 'the various forms of the place'

or biodiversity of species and ecosystems, the latter contributing to a variety of work. The **place value in relation to others** was noted in two contexts. At the site, which is part of a new community of like-minded individuals, this situation enhanced its overall value. In contrast, another site, located in a protected mountain landscape, the participant valued the expansive land and distance from neighbours, which offers a sense of freedom.

3.4.9. Existence

This benefit was mentioned by five participants, 10 times in total, and emerged without direct prompting. It highlights the permaculture site as a habitat for non-human life. **Wild zones** were described, like a ‘jungle for animals and bugs’ with climbers and no human interference. Three participants said leaving the site would be hard, especially if it was ploughed, highlighting its **natural value**. Some repurposed or preserved plants simply to ‘save them’. Species and habitats were appreciated for their **intrinsic worth**, with participants seeing themselves as active in their protection.

3.4.10. Maintenance of options

Maintenance of options was not part of the interview protocol but was mentioned 10 times by five participants. It centres on **recognising a ‘higher order’** connecting plants and animals, breaking this connection risks unknown consequences, as expressed by one. Others stressed the need to **respect** little-understood species, including ‘weeds’, that may have a function we do not know yet, and also to let nature evolve freely to support biodiversity. In permaculture, this often happens in edge zones where diversity and potential thrive, as stressed by the farmer. The theme also related to food self-provisioning—one participant felt secure knowing she could grow or forage food if shops closed. Seed saving was part of this benefit.

3.4.11. Relational values as lens for non-material benefits

I identified several overlapping relational values: eudaimonia, kinship, reciprocity and care, belonging and sense of home, harmony; and co-creation and initiation. They were 260 mentions of relational values, with respondents referencing them between seven and 40 times. These values are discussed in detail in my article, which is now under review. Here I would like to illustrate how RVs can illuminate non-material benefits and

explain them better. Figure 83 provides a summary of the connections between non-material benefits and relational values that underpin them.

Figure 83. Identified non-material benefits (legend on the left) supported by the RVs (legend on the right). The number of occurrences reflects how often a non-material benefit and corresponding RV co-occurred in the data.

The **eudaimonic value** in the behind of learning and knowledge relates both to the idea that others can learn to *‘do the right thing’* through the project, and to participants gaining knowledge they consider *‘good and fulfilling’* to learn. In the case of the activity benefit, a range of experiences—active, passive, and immersive—were described as fulfilling, either for the joy they bring, or the application of the *‘right’* principles. The identity benefit emerges from a sense of being in the *right place*, aligned with the *right social identity*, and from a resonance between permaculture practices and participants’ broader values, such as responsibility, respect, health, altruism and diversity. The aesthetic benefit is underpinned by a particular notion of *‘right’ beauty*—one that encompasses diversity, respects nature and its creatures, and includes the possibility of *creating* beauty in a way that reflects these values. The heritage benefit is supported by the possibility of continuing ancestral practices, modifying them, or doing things entirely differently, in ways that feel

'right' to the individual. The **bequest benefit** arises from activities oriented toward the future well-being of both people and nature, including the transmission of values and attitudes to the next generation.

Kinship value gives rise to the benefit of learning and knowledge, particularly through recognising more-than-human beings as integral parts of a whole system, which contributes to a welcoming relationship to them. Kinship also supports spirituality, expressed through a sense that humans *are* nature, and that all life is deeply interconnected. This value encourages an attitude of understanding rather than segregation. Identity benefit arises from living this kinship on daily basis, which resonates with the person deeply. Relational value of **reciprocity and care** supports learning and knowledge by fostering an understanding of mutual exchange between humans and ecosystems. This also supports identity, as respondents want to work with nature in a respectful and meaningful way—a relationship best expressed through the various activities they engage in.

The value of **belonging and sense of home** primarily supports identity benefits tied to physical place. It also reflects broader values such as responsibility, health, and security. The value of **harmony** supports learning and knowledge by suggesting that nature itself can teach us about harmony on many levels—ecological, social, aesthetical, and personal. The relational value of **co-creation and initiation** supports aesthetic benefit, with the site as a model for others and a space for practitioners to refine their approach. It also contributes to learning, offering visitors a real-world experience of co-creation.

4 Discussion

4.1. Material ecosystem services and benefits

Most of private sites were largely self-sufficient with vegetables, fruits and small fruits but production of other food types was either absent or insufficient, particularly animal products and staple foods such as rice, pasta, flour, grains, and mostly also potatoes. This is aligned with Reiff et al. (2025) that permaculture sites in Germany mostly produce vegetables. A comparison with hobby gardening provides some yield perspective: according to Jehlička et al. (2019) Czech households that grow food produce up to 34,8% of their vegetables consumption, 32,6% of fruit, 27,9% of potatoes and 27,4% of eggs. Permaculture practitioners in this study appeared to produce more vegetables and fruits, fewer potatoes, and more eggs than that.

The level of self-sufficiency was strongly dependent on diet. Households with vegetarian or vegan diets had to purchase more vegetables and legumes than others, but did not need to buy animal products. Less traditional foods also played a role: wild herbs and greens, as well as grains such as millet and buckwheat, were commonly used. More than half of the sites reported baking their own bread, compared with about one third of the general population in Czechia, who bake bread at least occasionally (CVVM, 2021). This suggests a somewhat atypical dietary pattern or approach to obtaining food, which is most likely linked to the non-material benefits discussed in the following section.

Such practices also suggest a positive impact of permaculture on reducing greenhouse gas emissions, both by shortening food transport chains (Michalský & Hooda, 2015) and by shifting dietary patterns. Even small changes in diet have been estimated to reduce environmental impact by around 8% (Tukker et al., 2011). Moreover, Lachat et al. (2018) found positive correlations between food species richness and nutritional quality, which suggests that permaculture, with its focus on diversity, may lead to healthier diets.

Direct comparisons between permaculture and conventional agriculture are, however, problematic. None of the studied sites produced typical agricultural crops such as grains or oil plants in large quantities. In addition, permaculture practitioners consider the

whole site as a single ecosystem, including areas with little direct yield for humans. This means that yield per unit area will always appear lower than in standard agricultural systems. Reiff et al. (2025) confirmed this, finding that permaculture might require 20% more land to achieve yields comparable to agriculture in general. However, compared with organic agriculture, it showed 44% higher productivity (ibid.)

Another important aspect is that private produce is shaped by many personal factors. Since cultivation is often not the practitioners' main employment and is not supported by subsidy schemes, production may fluctuate from year to year for personal or management reasons. As Stavi et al. (2016) note, the risk of crop failure is high even in professional organic management. Reiff et al. (2025) describes that German permaculture farms showed a high variability in productivity as well as lower yields caused by the low age of some of the systems. My findings confirm this.

It would be useful for future research to study the cultivated plants in greater detail, both to better capture the yield diversity and to examine how preferences for growing certain species align with dietary choices. If productivity on a private farm is to be measured, an ideal design would involve a study site with a simple family setting, allowing yield to be expressed on a per-person basis.

The only available produce data for S7 show that the farm produced 1,853 t/ha of vegetables, fruits, nuts and herbs and other 762 pc of vegetables per 1 ha and additional 4 700 eggs per 1,5 ha. The fact that part of the vegetables was counted in pieces does not allow for a total comparison, but for fruit and vegetables a typical yields per hectare are in range of 5 to 50 t/ha. Also here, the whole permaculture farm area is considered which makes comparisons with conventional, or even organic agriculture difficult. The diversity of planted crops is remarkable and much higher than in agroecology (12 crops) (Boeraeve et al., 2020) and aligns with findings of Flores and Buot in Ramamoorthy et al. (2022) who listed 45 species in the vegetable/cereal group per permaculture farm (present at 50% farms) and 61 multifunctional plant species, including fruit, per farm (present at 20% of them).

4.2. Regulating ecosystem services

This study found that permaculture ecosystems provide regulating services such as microclimate regulation, pest control, flood control, erosion control, and soil fertility, and that the level of capacity to deliver these services is higher than in conventional agriculture. Permaculture also supports biodiversity, which underpins these services.

Until recently, no studies had examined the impact of permaculture on ecosystem condition, which is crucial for its capacity to deliver ES. Krebs and Bach (2018) theoretically suggested that permaculture systems would contain more soil organic matter due to mulching practices, leading to a better soil fertility and smaller soil erosion. My findings confirm this and align with Williamson et al. (2024) who found 7,44 % and 9,33 % of SOC in permaculture in comparison with 1,81% of SOC in a conventional field. Similarly, Reiff et al. (2024) found a mean of SOC of 3,4% in permaculture soils and the present study revealed slightly higher values, with beds averaging 6,8% (median 4,6%) and edible forests averaging 3,9% (median 3,5%). While the control fields in both studies showed comparable SOC levels of around 2,0%, the relative enrichment under permaculture appears stronger here, particularly in the beds, where SOC more than tripled field values and exceeded previous estimates. Variation was more pronounced in my study. Whereas Reiff reported relatively narrow ranges (± 0.3), my results indicate pronounced heterogeneity, with SOC in beds ranging from 1,8% to 17,3% and edible forests from 1,9% to 7,2%. This suggests that permaculture systems can foster both exceptionally high SOC accumulation in certain sites as well as more moderate levels depending on local conditions and management. Other soil condition variables important for fertility were also generally better on permaculture than on the field reference units, such as bare soil, AWS, soil Ph and nutrient status.

Permaculture beds in my study provide regulating services of flood control and erosion control, confirming theoretical assumption that the usage of compost on permaculture sites will have these outcomes (Krebs & Bach, 2018). The magnitude and direction of land-use effects on soil-related ecosystem variables revealed a consistent pattern across multiple indicators. Compared to beds, fields showed markedly greater surface exposure, significantly lower SOC, reduced IR, and smaller AWS, together forming a clear land-use pattern of exposed surfaces and reduced capacity to retain and supply water.

Interestingly, edible forests reduced bare soil but did not consistently translate this protection into improved IR, similar to woodland. In particular, woodlands showed significantly lower WFC than beds, suggesting that the relationship between surface cover and hydraulic properties is influenced by other factors. Wooded and edible-forest systems clearly reduce exposed soil but do not uniformly guarantee higher infiltration or WFC. This indicates that targeted interventions—such as alleviating compaction, promoting root penetration, or modifying litter management—may be necessary to optimise hydrological function.

My results confirm Reiff et al. (2024) in showing that site-level heterogeneity was high for several variables. Random-effect and site-only analyses indicated that IR and SOC varied strongly among sites, with some (e.g. S3) markedly lower and others (e.g. S5) markedly higher than the baseline. WFC also differed systematically across sites. This underscores that local geomorphological and managerial factors—including soil texture, stoniness, historical disturbance, and microtopography—can be as important as land use in determining hydraulic and carbon dynamics. Conversely, the weak site-only explanatory power for bare soil and AWS suggests that land-use contrasts dominate these responses, although some site-specific effects (e.g. S2 for bare soil) warrant cautious interpretation.

Microclimate regulation in permaculture appeared slightly better than in conventional fields, but the distribution of data loggers allows only a tentative suggestion of trends. Edible forests performed better than beds, and beds generally performed better than fields, but at no site were these three sampling places measured together. Mollison and Holmgren (1978) expected microclimate regulation to be high in permaculture, and my study cannot fully confirm this.

Pest control as an ecosystem service in permaculture was generally high and confirmed theoretical assumptions (Krebs & Bach, 2018; McLennon et al., 2021), showing higher predation rates than conventional fields. When field sampling places were close to a field margin (S6, S8), predation rates improved. This suggests that landscape heterogeneity is crucial for this service, as it promotes biodiversity (Marshall & Moonen, 2002). In terms of biodiversity and habitat diversity, permaculture outperformed the other reference units. Up to 16 different habitat types were observed, and plant diversity was higher

in permaculture—by 217% in beds and 284% in edible forests—compared to fields, with woodlands also performing better than fields. Hirschfeld and Van Acker (2020) also studied species richness on permaculture sites, reporting between 12 and 38 species on a 5 m² plot. Although their sampling place choices were similar to mine, they used larger plots, so a direct comparison is not possible. My study can only confirm the trend that permaculture supports biodiversity. Measurement of perennality and an overall food species diversity would be my suggestion for a future research, following Hirschfeld and van Acker (2020) to enable comparison and provide more data.

Despite confirming the delivery of at least five regulating services by permaculture ecosystems, this study is observational and limited to the sampled variables and covariates. Statistical analysis of soil-related variables revealed large p-values for some interactions and occasional negative R² values in site-only models, reflecting boundary conditions such as low statistical power or residual variance structure. Some covariates were not measured—including soil texture (only estimated), bulk density, root biomass, and land-use history. These likely contributed to residual variation and should be addressed in future work. To strengthen mechanistic inference, future research should combine finer vertical sampling, repeated temporal measurements, and inclusion of important soil covariates.

The inclusion of as many permaculture sites as possible is also a limitation. While many results are available, they do not allow full explanation of outliers or deviations. For biophysical variable measurement, I suggest including fewer farms but studying them more deeply in future research. A major weakness was insufficient access to fields and information about their history. As a result, the unit ‘field’ in this study included sites managed maybe more ecologically than others. Soil-type differences should ideally have been avoided but were not.

4.3. Non-material benefits

My research offered the first comprehensive evaluation of non-material benefits and their underpinning relational values in European permaculture ecosystems, addressing a research gap in empirical research on their role in sustainable food futures and agroecological transition. Permaculture provides practitioners with benefits of learning and knowledge, activity, identity, aesthetics, heritage, spirituality, bequest, sense of place,

existence and maintenance of options. This breadth suggests that permaculture contributes to human well-being as a multifunctional food-growing system that maintains and enhances diverse ES. Similar diversity of well-being perspectives—ecological, socio-cultural and agricultural has been observed in the Philippines and Australia (Joshua Flores and Buot 2023; Nanni 2023). The discovered multifunctionality aligns with projections for the future of agroecosystems (Garbach et al. 2014) and supports Landis’s (2017) argument that less intensified landscapes yield more cultural ES. It also responds to Gordon’s (2025) observation that relational values are often latent in the literature: my findings show empirically how they motivate permaculture practice. Interestingly, such diversity of cultural ES has not been observed among non-specified farmers (Cheng et al., 2025) or conventional farmers (Quinn et al. 2015).

Learning and knowledge emerged as the most prominent and cross-cutting non-material benefit, closely intertwined with activity, identity, spirituality, and aesthetics. This reflects permaculture’s *strength as an educational framework*, engaging practitioners through hands-on ‘life-long learning’ (Centemeri, 2019; Henfrey, 2018; Martín et al., 2023; Nanni, 2023). Similar patterns of embodied learning are also found in regenerative agriculture where it fosters sense of place (Gordon et al., 2025; Vizquete et al., 2025). Cheng (2025) also found that (non-specified) farmers placed particular importance on scientific and educational value, suggesting these stakeholders appreciate particularly this aspect of their work. The distinctive feature of permaculture learning is *systems thinking* (Holmgren 2002). This fosters biodiversity-friendly practices and cultivates a holistic worldview in which people, nature, and the planet are interconnected, so that harm to one affects all. This contrasts with conventional farmers, who rarely connect ES to biodiversity or ecological functions (Quinn et al. 2015). It aligns with West’s (2020) argument that today’s environmental crises stem from a cognitive disconnect between people and ecosystems, and that systems thinking can help re-establish a deeper connection with nature.

The connection between learning and eudaimonic relational value was clear in my study: *knowledge gained through permaculture becomes part of what practitioners regard as a ‘good life’* and is often shared with others.

Aesthetic appreciation in permaculture is closely linked to ecological understanding. In my study, the knowledge about the value of diverse elements and their functions,

including supporting biodiversity and system resilience, inform a specific notion of aesthetics, also linked to existence and maintenance of options. This conception of beauty contrasts with Balázs's (2021) findings among cross-sectoral experts, for whom aesthetics was the primary cultural ES related to work around agro-landscapes. It also differs from the 'neat and tidy' ideal identified among conventional farmers who express care this way (Chapman et al. 2019). My participants valued the visual appeal of 'naturalness' instead and supported the existence of untended areas as part of a healthy, resilient system. Bare soil, monocultures, and raked leaves were described as unappealing, whereas structural diversity and visible ecological processes were appreciated. This seems to align with aesthetics value in Assandri et al. (2018), where public favoured biodiversity-rich landscapes characterized by dry-stone walls, marginal habitats and high land-cover diversity.

The benefit of identity and eudaimonic RV show the permaculture site becoming part of practitioners' sense of self—a place to live out values of a 'good life' that extends identity to non-human beings (kinship). The RV of reciprocity and care highlights sustainable, organic land management as a priority. The benefit of spirituality—where 'everything is one' and humans are part of 'something bigger'—reveals a worldview opposite to the entrenched dualism between humans and nature identified by White (1967) as a root of the modern ecological crisis. Influences of 'older religious cultures' (Holmgren 2012) are apparent, fostering biodiversity protection similar to traditional sacred groves (Irvine in Marselle et al. 2019). Spiritual well-being, encompassing wholeness, is strongly supported by permaculture practice. The human–nature relationship is described as 'participation in the whole system', 'cooperation', 'complementation', 'harmony', or 'partnership'. Similar spiritual and ethical meanings of permaculture have been discussed as 'dark green religion' by Caraway (2018), Hathaway (2015) and as 'nature spirituality' by Kolářová (2023). My data indicate that many participants operate within *transactional worldviews that are relational*, rather than purely systemic (West et al. 2020).

For permaculture practitioners, heritage was mainly linked to *family traditions* one or two generations back, often experienced in childhood. These traditions were selectively adopted, with practitioners choosing which elements to retain and which to leave behind. Similar to van den Born et al. (2018), permaculture fosters reconnection with nature and outdoor activities motivated by eudaimonic value and curiosity. Vizquete (2025) found the

same as 'individual identity' RV among agroecological participants. Bequest was also important but rather than focusing solely on passing on tangible assets, many practitioners prioritised *transmitting RVs*, such as relationship to nature and its role in a good life, to future generations. Sense of place was tied to 'home', encompassing both the built and the natural elements of the land, including wilder areas. This aligns with Centemeri's (2019) emphasis on the '*reinhabiting process*' in permaculture, drawing on Holmgren's (2011) work linking it to long-term inhabitation and sustainability in indigenous societies. Several respondents stated that if they had to leave their current site, they would start again elsewhere. This resonates with West's (2020) argument that rather than 'reconnecting with the biosphere', it may be more accurate to speak of '*re-enacting the biosphere*'—underscoring the embeddedness of human–nature relationships in place-based contexts.

Analysing the non-material benefits of practicing permaculture through the lens of relational values helped clarify underlying motivations and contributions. It showed that permaculture mobilises these values and supports a pluralistic worldview, aligning with its ethical principles. My findings resonate with Vizuite et al. (2025), who conclude that plurality and assembled appearance of values is key to bottom-up agroecological transitions that care for biodiversity and fellow humans. The most important asset of permaculture in fostering pro-environmental attitudes is the whole-systems thinking (part of the learning and knowledge benefit) that supports all other benefits and spans the spectrum of relational values, underpinned by permaculture ethical principles. Because learning in permaculture is rapid (Nanni, 2023) it could inform educational activities for farmers interested in cultural ES but lacking agroecological knowledge (Plieninger et al., 2015).

5 Conclusion

The research questions of this thesis were addressed by the study. To address RQ1 and partly RQ2, I conclude that permaculture provides ecosystem services spanning all three domains—material, regulating, and non-material—and can therefore be considered a multifunctional agroecosystem. Its strongest potential lies in non-material benefits, where the array of contributions is the widest. These benefits shape practices that sustain and support diversity and enhance regulating services essential for resilience, as confirmed by this study. The lowest potential, compared with conventional agriculture on a per-area basis, was found in material benefits. Permaculture primarily provides vegetables and fruits, and privately managed sites do not aim to grow certain crops or animal products. Commercial sites also concentrate rather on fruits, nuts and vegetables. This limitation may be partly offset by dietary shifts and pro-environmental behaviour, which influence purchasing choices for food not produced through permaculture. Nonetheless, this would require permaculture to be integrated into broader frameworks such as agroecology or organic farming. On the other hand, it is not clear if regulating services would have the same extent if the growing area was used more extensively.

The sub-question of RQ1 cannot be answered fully, as findings were complex and context-dependent. Most regulating services in permaculture were similar to those of natural ecosystems, yet had to be enhanced to sustain food production—just as food yields themselves must exceed natural baselines. At some sites, permaculture outperformed conventional fields only slightly in certain regulating services. Non-material benefits did not align solely with either nature or agriculture, but instead provided a distinctive basis for human–nature relationships, resembling those found in practitioners doing regenerative agriculture.

To answer RQ2, I conclude that permaculture is a promising candidate for inspiring nature-based approaches within mainstream agriculture (Vanbergen et al. 2020) and can strengthen the resilience of agroecosystems. The permaculture approach is inherently relational, and the RVs it fosters are grounded in sustainability-aligned broad values such as responsibility, health, respect, and prosperity. These values are critical when negotiating trade-offs among ecosystem services within socio-ecological food systems.

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7 List of Appendices

7.1. Appendix I: Field measurements protocol

Postup pro praktickou část výzkumu

DEN 1	1. INFILTRACE (schopnost vsakování) Metoda: double ring infiltrometr.
PO 24 HODINÁCH / DEN 2	2. PVK (WFC) WATER FIELD CAPACITY – OBJEMOVÁ VLHKOST PŮDY Množství vody, které je půda dlouhodobě schopná zadržet. Kopeckého válečky 100 ml. Dám do prostoru vnitřního kruhu infiltrometru. Vezmu vzorky z různých hloubek: 0-5 cm, 10-15 cm, 25-30 cm. Půdu z nich dám do pytlíků.
PO 24 HODINÁCH / DEN 2 / DOMA	Buď odnesu do laborky nebo doma: zvážím, usuším (105 °C, 5 hod), zvážím. Uschovám pro další. 3. Prosít na 2 mm sítu. Zvážit. Dostanu PODÍL AGREGÁTŮ. Hrubé dát do hmoždíře, zase prosít. 5 agregátů dát stranou a
V ZIMĚ / MIMO SEZÓNU	4. v zimě měřit VODOSTABILITU AGREGÁTŮ. (5 agregátů z každého vzorku). Agregáty mají mezi sebou kapilární páry..
DEN 1	5. UKLÁDÁNÍ UHLÍKU. Vše z bodu 2 si schovám.
červenec/ srpen	6. PEST CONTROL. Opatřím si modelový hmyz. Silikonem nalepím. 3 terče dám do místa <u>permakultury</u> , 3 terče do lesa, 3 do pole.

PO 24
HODINÁCH
/ DEN 2

Druhý den posbírám, zjistím, kolik toho bylo predátory sežráno.

DEN 1

7. MICROCLIMATE CONTROL

Pohledem – procento holé půdy. Kolik procent zabere pokryv. Plocha, kterou budu sledovat, může být 1 m², ale budou-li to v permazahradě záhony, tak radši 0,5m x 0,5m. Přizpůsobím sledovanou plochu té nejmenší.

Lze pomocí obruče.

Umístit datalogery

JARO

8. MÍRA VĚTRNÉ EROZE

Umístit na celý rok

Metoda: erosimeter (tyčka s trnem a praporkem)

červenec/
srpen

9. BIODIVERZITA

Vegetační snímek v době maximální vegetace.

Metoda: obruč.

Les: běžně 5x5 m, pole běžně 1x1m.

Pokud dřevitá vegetace, odhadnu ji na 5 m extra.

7.2. Appendix II: Predation protocol

Predation: CARDS IN

PISTINA

Date 19.6.2019	Visit number	Observers
Landscape Field	Sampling site	
Distance line 1 from border:	GPS (middle of line 1)	
Distance line 2 from border:	GPS (middle of line 2)	
Crop type in sample field oat/over	Crop height in sample field	
Crop type in adjacent field	Crop height in adjacent field	
Time cards in place: 1315		

Predation: CARDS OUT

Date 20.6.19	Visit number	Observers
Landscape:	Sampling site:	
Time cards out: 1530		

Cards recovered

		Recovered	Not Recovered	Reason if not recovered	Nb aphids predated
Line 1	Card 1	✓			0
	Card 2	✓			0
	Card 3	✓			0
	Card 4	✓			0
	Card 5	✓			0
Line 2	Card 6	✓			1
	Card 7	✓			0
	Card 8	✓			1
	Card 9	✓			0
	Card 10	✓			1

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7.3. Appendix III: Semi-structured interview protocol

Warm-up

How was it in when you first learned about permaculture?

The land

What happens when you enter it here?

Which feelings do you mostly have on this land?

When you are not here and you are thinking about this land, what comes first to your mind? Why is it important for you?

What does this land mean to you?

Which place on this land do you like the most?

Why do you like returning there?

What is so great about sitting (working) there?

When you are (sitting) there, what comes up to your mind? What happens when you get up afterwards?

What is your typical day on this land?

Have you thought about what this land is giving to you? What else?

And when all this is done and finished, how will this be for you?

Non-material benefits

Aesthetics

How do you value this place from an aesthetical point of view?

What do you aesthetically like the most here?

Do you like this more than the garden of your parents? / the garden of the neighbours (or what came up)

Do people come here? What do they say about the appearance of the garden?

Do you invite public here?

Cultural heritage

When you work in this place do you connect with somebody from the past? Do you think of somebody from the past?

Do you do something in here that is not absolutely permaculture but that reminds you of someone who did it before you?

What is your motivation (vision) when creating this garden? (e.g. 'the garden of the old times.')

Is there a particular plant or animal that connect you with something/somebody? Is there a plant that has a national or local meaning for you?

Identity

Can you imagine leaving it here?

What would you miss?

Are there places here that are important for how you understand identity?

Are there some places that remind you about important events in the past that are important for your community/family/group?

Place value

Are there some places on your land that are important for you but not because they are giving you any tangible profit?

Spirituality

Is there a place where you feel something special in the sense of inspiring you that there are powers or entities that are bigger than ourselves? I know this is a personal question but if it is not a problem for you could you describe me some of these experiences you had at this place?

Would you say there is a sacred place on this land? Does this place have a name?

Do you see an animal, plant or a stone like sacred here? Do they have a name?

Physical and experiential interactions

Do you experiment in the garden with something?

Do you observe in the garden something/somebody regularly?

Intellectual and representative interactions

Do you make notes about something in the garden?

Do you (or someone else) learn something in the garden? Do you have an experience when you had the feeling that the garden or a place in it is teaching you something?

Bequest

Do you have some experiences with this land where you hope that your children or other children from the area will also have?

Do you feel the need to keep and save plants, animals, ecosystems for the sake of preserving them for other generations?

Do you think this is your duty? Or generally the duty of us, humans?

Artistic inspiration

Has this place ever inspired you for an artistic or creative visual activity? (An idea or a picture?) (Gould et al.)

Nonphysical value of activities

Is there anything intangible that you get from this place/garden that you see as a benefit for you and that is part of the physical activities that you do here?

And the last question:

Imagine that you need.... (the food they grow and like) ...You can grow it yourself or buy it in a shop. What will you choose? How will you decide? Why would you decide this way? What would you gain by this decision and what would you lose by this decision?

